

**13th Annual Symposium by
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN (ISAJ)**

Frontiers of Materials, Life & Earth Sciences and Beyond

PROGRAM AND ABSTRACTS

18 NOVEMBER 2022

**Main Auditorium, Embassy of India,
Tokyo, Japan**

Indian Scientists Association in Japan

特定非営利活動法人

(NPO Reg. No. 0503-05-001817)

<http://www.isaj.org>

ISAJ is registered as a Japanese non-profit organization (NPO) under Japan's NPO law. Tsukuba has been decided to be ISAJ's headquarter. The Executive Body is ISAJ's governing body and is responsible for directing the affairs and determining the future of the society. The Executive Body will appoint some of the Executive Body members to take responsibilities such as the Chapter Presidents of six different regions in Japan (Hokkaido, Tohoku, Tokyo, Tsukuba, Fukuoka, and Osaka).

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The Ambassador of India to Japan

Honorary Advisor:

Counsellor (Science & Technology), Embassy of India, Japan

Advisor (*komon*):

Sai Hira India Foundation (SHIF)

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H.E. Mr. Sibi George,
The Ambassador of India, Japan

Honorary Advisor

Counsellor (S&T),
Embassy of India, Japan

Adviser (*komon*)

Sai Hira India Foundation (SHIF)

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Dr. Elango Chandiran

Dr. Digvijay Singh

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Messages

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MESSAGE

I am happy to extend my best wishes to the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) for its Thirteenth Symposium at Vivekananda Cultural Centre, Tokyo, on November 18, 2022.

I am happy to note that ISAJ is a forum that enables young Indian researchers and students to gain a broader perspective by connecting with scientists and research institutions in Japan. In this context, this year's theme is aptly titled "Frontiers of Materials, Life and Earth Sciences and Beyond". The theme has great relevance to both India and Japan as we deepen our engagement in Science and Technology. The new knowledge derived and exchanged among the disciplines and across the institutions would help find innovative solutions for some of the challenges faced by humanity and the environment.

I sincerely hope that the Indian and Japanese scientific fraternity will utilize to utmost the unique platform of ISAJ.

I am confident that the scientific deliberations during the Symposium would lead to constructive recommendations for enhancing the strategic partnership between the two countries.

I wish the Symposium a grand success.

(Sibi George)

Tokyo
November 10, 2022

MESSAGE

Dr. Kazuhiro Hono

President, National Institute for Materials Science, Japan

On behalf of the National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), Japan, it is my great pleasure to congratulate Indian Scientists Association in Japan for holding their 13th Annual Symposium titled “Frontiers of Materials, Life & Earth Sciences and Beyond.”

This year marks 70 years of diplomatic relations between India and Japan. Since then, Japan and India have enjoyed close friendship and mutual trust, and close cooperation in many areas, which has acquired more significance in the recent times. One of the important areas of cooperation is in the field of science and technology, which is still developing and holds tremendous future.

NIMS is at the forefront of academic collaborations with India. We have concluded an agreement for International Cooperative Graduate Program with four universities (Anna University, IIT-Hyderabad, IIT-Guwahati, and IIT-Varanasi) since 2007 and accepted many excellent students through this program so far. In 2021, we established “IITH-NIMS Joint Center for Materials Science” as a new scheme and accelerating close cooperation with IITH.

I appreciate the efforts of the Indian Scientists Association in Japan in bringing participants from various universities and scientific institutions in Japan, and those under various programs between Japan and India, on to a common platform through their annual symposiums for an exchange of ideas and information. I wish this symposium a great success!

On behalf of the ISAJ, we would like to take this opportunity to welcome all the delegates and guests to the 13th Annual Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). The theme of this year's symposium is "Frontiers of Materials, Life & Earth Sciences and Beyond". ISAJ, a Non-profit Organization (NPO), was conceived in 2008 as a community forum by coming together of many Indian scientists working in Japan, and formally inaugurated by Dr. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India, in the presence of His Excellency Hemant Krishan Singh, the then Ambassador of India, in January 2009. It has come a long way since then. Registered as a NPO in Japan in 2010, ISAJ has been functioning to promote seminars, community discussions, and networking at all levels: from undergraduate students to academic/industrial professionals. This bridging function has connected many scientists and researchers, helped several young Indian students to get professional training and experience in Japan, and has played successful role in India-Japan Science & Technology cooperation.

Annual symposium has been a highlight of ISAJ activities continuously for the past 12 years. We are proud to celebrate its 13th anniversary today. As in every year, the symposium, is planned to highlight the research being carried out by Indian researchers and their colleagues in Japan. Every year, we have had large participation from multidisciplinary fields. The first seven symposia were held at the main auditorium of the Embassy of India in Tokyo, followed by the eighth one in Tokyo University campus, the ninth in AIST Tsukuba campus, and for the tenth, it moved to the Kansai region, the Osaka university campus. The eleventh was held online due the COVID pandemic but breaking physical barriers. The 12th Annual Symposium was held in a hybrid mode (on-site and online) at Shimizu, Shizuoka City, hosted by the Tokai University. We are organizing this year's event at the Embassy of India after a gap of five years, considering the Importance of the year for both our countries when India and Japan celebrate *70 years of formal diplomatic relations*, especially when we celebrate *75 years of Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav* (75 years of independence of India).

As in the previous years, we have maintained the interdisciplinary format of the symposium, offering opportunity to many participants for exchange of ideas and experiences. Through the scientific contents of the presentations over the years, the diverse and expanding scientific and technological areas in which the Indian researchers are working in Japan is clearly visible. It can also be observed that over the years more and more Indian researchers are moving up as young researchers and faculty in Japan, as well as moving to positions in prestigious universities in India.

We take this opportunity to welcome our guests and are looking forward to intense interactions. Young researchers' presentations have been the highlight of our earlier symposia and continue to be so this year. We also look forward to hearing from the senior scientists on their long-term experiences working in Japan and positive contributions towards India-Japan science and technology cooperation. We sincerely believe that this is a unique opportunity for all of us to interact and learn beyond our daily activities and our specialized roles in research. We have no doubt that coming together on this platform will benefit young Indian students and researchers in several ways.

Our gratitude to His Excellency Mr. Sibi George, Ambassador of India to Japan and other dignitaries for joining us for the 13th annual symposium. We are sincerely thankful to all our guests for accepting our invitation and coming all the way to contribute to this event. We sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium and make best of this excellent opportunity to interact with each other and strengthen India-Japan S&T ties with new friendships and collaborations.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman, ISAJ

Alok Singh
Vice-Chairman, ISAJ

Welcome Message from the Conveners

We, the conveners, would like to warmly welcome our esteemed guests and all participants to the 13th ISAJ Annual Symposium on “Frontiers of Materials, Life & Earth Sciences and Beyond” being organized on the 75th anniversary of India’s independent, and 70 years of India-Japan formal diplomatic relations. It is our great privilege to be organizing the symposium in a fully in-person mode after three years due to the COVID-19. We are grateful to all participants for sharing our enthusiasm in supporting this symposium by presenting their research findings. We are aware that some of you have traveled long distances to be here today. We are happy to have received an overwhelming response for in-person presentations. We express our gratitude to the plenary and invited speakers for accepting our invitation readily, despite a rather short notice. We are overwhelmed by response to our call for abstracts from participants of various nationalities (India, Italy, France, Ukraine, Indonesia, etc., and, of course, Japan) associated with academic and research institutions across Japan.

This symposium brings together eminent researchers, professors, young faculty members, and young researchers from diverse fields of science and technology. The sessions are planned to be multidisciplinary in nature to allow experts and young researchers from diverse backgrounds to share their expertise, thereby providing a unique opportunity to learn outside of our specialized domains and to innovate our ideas and research outcomes for the benefit of science and society. Introduced in the last year, the ISAJ Lifetime Achievement Award-2022 is to be presented in the inaugural session of the symposium. For the encouragement of young researchers, Best Poster Awards will be presented in the closing ceremony, as in the previous years. We would like to thank the members of the Symposium Organizing Committee for extending their unstinted support for this symposium.

We will continue to seek your assistance in improving this annual symposium in the future and we welcome all suggestions and recommendations for making it even better. It is our sincere wish that this ISAJ Symposium gives you a momentum to keep on going with your research work in these post-pandemic times. Please enjoy all the exciting session during this one-day event.

Thank you, and welcome again!

Dr. Elango Chandiran

Convener

Dr. Digvijay Singh

Convener

Frontiers of Materials, Life & Earth Sciences and Beyond

13th Annual ISAJ Symposium

November 18, 2022 (Friday)

Main Auditorium, Embassy of India, Tokyo, Japan

Time	PROGRAM	
9:00 -9:25	PARTICIPANTS REGISTRATION	
9:30 – 10:05	INAUGURAL SESSION	
9:30	Welcome Address	Dr. Sunil Kaul, Chairman, ISAJ
9:40	Conveners' Address	Dr. Elango Chandiran, Dr. Digvijay Singh
9:45	Inaugural Address	H.E. Mr. Sibi George, The Ambassador of India to Japan
9:55	Awards Presentation	ISAJ Lifetime achievement award
10:00	Vote of Thanks	Dr. Alok Singh, Vice-Chairman, ISAJ
10:05 - 10:30	PHOTO SESSION & TEA/COFFEE BREAK	
10:30-12:10	SESSION I CHAIR: Dr. Renu Wadhwa (AIST), Prof. Sakthi Kumar (Toyo Univ.)	
10:30	Tadaaki Nagao , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Carbon Dots as Sustainable Materials for UV Screener, Direct White Light Emitter, and Laser</i>	
10:50	Michio Kawamiya , The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC) <i>Earth system modeling for projecting the changing planet</i>	
11:10	Kazutoshi Iijima , Yokohama National University <i>Aggregation Behavior of Polysaccharide Composite Particles and Application for Tissue Engineering</i>	

11:30	Vamsi K. Komarala , Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi <i>Fabrication and characterization of carrier-selective contact based silicon solar cells</i>
11:45	Yuji Teramura , National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>Cell Surface Engineering with Biocompatible Polymers for Biomedical Applications</i>
12:00	Ruma Mandal , Tohoku University <i>Magnetization Dynamics Study of High PMA Ultrathin Magnetic Heterostructures: A TRMOKE Study</i>
12:10 - 13:40	LUNCH & POSTER SESSION Chairs: Dr. Digvijay Singh (NIMS), Dr. Vickey Nandal (NIMS)
13:40 – 15:40	SESSION II CHAIR: Prof. Atsushi Suzuki (YNU), Dr. Aaditya Manjanath (NIMS)
13:40	Manish Biyani , Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (JAIST) <i>Can we predict the next pandemic?</i>
13:55	Jonathan Hill , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Novel Functional Organic Chromophores</i>
14:15	Hideyuki Murakami , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>High Entropy Alloys for High Temperature Applications</i>
14:35	Toru Hara , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Electron microscopy techniques developed in NIMS for materials research</i>
14:45	Sachiko Hayashida , Research Institute for Humanity and Nature (RIHN) <i>Aakash project: toward clear air over the world</i>
15:00	Hena Das , Tokyo Institute of Technology <i>Mechanisms at the level of atoms and electrons that drive electric field control over magnetism</i>
15:15	Sae Matsunaga , The University of Tokyo <i>High temperature materials: Ni-based superalloys and beyond</i>
15:30	Bhaskar Dasgupta , Tokyo University <i>Hybrid of experiment and computation for the interpretation of biomolecular sequence and structural data</i>
15:40 - 16:00	TEA/COFFEE BREAK

16:00-17:40	SESSION III CHAIR: Dr. Swadhin Behera (JAMSTEC), Dr. Kedarnath Mahapatra (Tokai U.)	
16:00	Masayoshi Higuchi , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Electrochromic Metallo-Supramolecular Polymers</i>	
16:20	Atsushi Suzuki , Yokohama National University <i>Smart Hydrogels with Excellent Swelling and Mechanical Properties for Realistic Medical Simulators</i>	
16:30	Subbiah Alwarappan , CSIR-CERI, India, & University of Tsukuba <i>Electrochemical Biosensors</i>	
16:45	Mahesh K. Kaushik , University of Tsukuba <i>Orexin, sleep, and narcolepsy; The discovery received the 2023 "Breakthrough Prize"</i>	
17:00	V Srivani , Jichi Medical University <i>Multi-Therapeutic Applications of Engineered Phage Capsids</i>	
17:10	Akhilesh babu Ganganboina , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Nanostructured photoelectrochemical platform probing visible light-driven virus detection</i>	
17:20	Md Emrul Kayesh , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Coadditive Engineering for Stable Sn-based provskite solar cells</i>	
17:30	Aaditya Manjanath , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Probing chemical reaction dynamics through excited-state time-dependent GW simulations</i>	
17:40-18:00	SESSION IV: SELECTED POSTERS Oral Presentations CHAIR: Dr. Asima Sultana (AIST), Dr. Elango Chandiran (NIMS)	
4 mins. each	PS-1	Hisay Lama , The University of Tokyo <i>Glassy Phase in Dense Bacteria Population</i>
	PS-2	Deeksha Arya , The University of Tokyo <i>Multinational advancements for AI-driven road inspection</i>
	PS-3	Pooja Gusain , Keio University <i>Violet light modulates mood behavior via non-visual retinal opsin OPN5</i>
	PS-4	Rahul Bhardwaj , Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (JAIST) <i>Nafion's Proton Transport in Cathode Catalyst Layer of Hydrogen Fuel Cell</i>
	PS-5	Huang Tianwei , The University of Tokyo <i>Modification of extracellular vesicles with oligopeptide for selective interaction with activated endothelium</i>
18:00	CLOSING SESSION & POSTER AWARDS	

LIST OF POSTER PRESENTATIONS	
PS-6	Thaviti Naidu Pallela , Tokyo Metropolitan University <i>Influence of yttrium micro-addition on microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of IN718 fabricated by selective laser melting</i>
PS-7	He Huifu , AIST-INDIA DAILAB & University of Tsukuba <i>Experimental evidence to the anti-migration activity of Cucurbitacin-B</i>
PS-8	Shi Yang , AIST-INDIA DAILAB & University of Tsukuba <i>A novel small molecule that inhibits proliferation and migration of cancer cells</i>
PS-9	Huayue Zhang , AIST-INDIA DAILAB & University of Tsukuba <i>In vitro experimental evidence to the anti-stress activity in a popular carotenoid fucoxanthin</i>
PS-10	Nadiia Velychkivska , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Multi-Responsive Star-Shaped Porphyrin-PNIPAM Conjugates</i>
PS-11	Pietro Beretta Piccoli , Nihon University <i>Environmental improvements from alternative gravel mounts in channelized rivers</i>
PS-12	Soumyaranjan Ratha , Akita University <i>Development of Multiferroic BiFeO₃ based Thin Films with Excellent Magnetic Properties for Reduction of Energy Consumption in Magnetic Devices</i>
PS-13	Yuya Sato , University of Tokyo <i>Manipulation of liposome by spontaneous incorporation of cell-penetrating peptide</i>
PS-14	Shaoji Liang , The University of Tokyo <i>Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4Zr-4Nb alloys fabricated by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS)</i>
PS-15	S.Vadivel , Tokyo Institute of Technology <i>Graphitic carbon nitride-based nanoplatfoms for environmental applications: design strategies and applications</i>
PS-16	Dennis Jodi , National Institute for Materials Science & Kyushu University <i>Suppressed Dislocation Density in Single-Crystal Pure Ni Fabricated via Laser Powder Bed Fusion with a Flat-Top Laser Profile</i>
PS-17	Han Hanlin , University of Tsukuba <i>The Stability of Nanobubble Water at Different Temperatures during Long Time Preservation</i>
PS-18	Sun Yixin , University of Tsukuba <i>Effect of nanobubbles water on microenvironment to improve liver steatosis</i>
PS-19	Silvia Pomes , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Characterization of plasticity initiation phenomena in Zr-based bulk metallic glass via nanoindentation</i>

PS-20	Gao Baoqi , University of Tsukuba <i>Dewatering performance of digested sludge by layered double hydroxides (LDHs) conditioning and its phosphorus recovery potential assessment</i>
PS-21	Zhang Weixu , University of Tsukuba <i>The Physical Features and Stability of Nanobubble Waters in Continuous Observations</i>
PS-22	Srinithi. A. K , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) & University of Tsukuba <i>Microstructure Engineering Towards the Development of SmFe12-based Permanent Magnets</i>
PS-23	Kunal Kumar , The University of Tokyo <i>Unraveling how the emission and Raman spectra of [Au(SCN)2]- dimeric and trimeric moieties are affected by aurophillic interaction</i>
PS-24	Liu Fei , University of Tsukuba <i>A study of changes in parents educational psychology caused by changes in educational policies in China and Japan</i>
PS-25	Santra Dines Chandra , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Promising Metallo-supramolecular Electrochromic Materials and Devices for Future Smart Window</i>
PS-26	Afshan Begum , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Observation of Isotropic Photonic Double Dirac Cones by High Angle-Resolution Reflection Spectroscopy at the Mid-Infrared Frequencies</i>
PS-27	Vanshita Sharma , Toyama Prefectural University <i>Construction of in vivo system for predicting human CYP24A1-dependent metabolism</i>
PS-28	V N Ramakrishnan , Vellore Institute of Technology <i>Analog/RF Performance Analysis of GaSb-InP Vertical Tunnel Field Effect Transistors</i>
PS-29	Atanu Panda , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Phosphorus-decorated Mo-MXene/CQD hybrid: a 2D/0D architecture for bifunctional electrochemical water splitting</i>
PS-30	Barun Kumar Barman , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Chromaticity Tunable White-Light-Emitting Carbon Dots via N-Dopant Site Formulation</i>
PS-31	Manoj Talluri , IIT Hyderabad & National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Giant Spin Pumping at Ferromagnet (Permalloy) - Organic Semiconductor (Perylene diimide) Interface</i>
PS-32	Sagar Saren , Kyushu University <i>Effect of Pore Size Distribution on Carbon Dioxide Adsorption in Activated Carbon: A Grand Canonical Monte Carlo Simulation Study</i>
PS-33	Satoko Kise , Toyama Prefectural University <i>The possibility of the gene therapy for rickets type II alopecia using adenovirus vector</i>

PS-34	Bageshree K , Tokyo Institute of Technology <i>Drought Impact Assessment Using Multivariate Drought Index and Relation with Socioeconomic Security of Farmers</i>
PS-35	Volkan Kilinc , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Low concentrated ions detection in complex medium with high ionic strength: example of cesium detection in seawater.</i>
PS-36	Vikas Nandal , National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>Unveiling charge carrier distribution in Al doped SrTiO₃ photocatalyst with quantum efficiency of unity</i>
PS-37	Ravi Gautam , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Nanocrystalline Soft Magnetic Material for Automotive Applications</i>
PS-38	Hemam Rachna Devi , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) <i>Rational design of two-dimensional multi-metallic based nanostructures for efficient water oxidation</i>
PS-39	Megha Sharma , Heriot-Watt University <i>How Emotions Improve Music Generation</i>
PS-40	Rajalakshmi Balasubramanian , Tokyo Institute of Technology <i>Characterization of The Sulfide-Responsive Transcriptional Factor YgaV In Escherichia coli.</i>
PS-41	Yoko Yamagami , Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC) <i>Sea level variability along the western coast of India simulated in a high-resolution ocean general circulation model</i>
PS-42	Yuji Ishida , The University of Tokyo <i>The effect of β/α strength ratio and volume fraction of β for fatigue properties of Ti-alloys</i>
PS-43	Samrat Mukherjee , Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology & National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>Functional Analysis of Chloride Ion Channel Clc1 in Cancer Invasion</i>
PS-44	Alisha Yadav , Kyoto University <i>Potassium-based Dual Carbon Battery using Pure Ionic Liquid Electrolyte</i>
PS-45	Nazrul Hisham Nazaruddin , Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology & National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>Stiffness Analysis via Atomic Force Microscopy for Microneedle Arrays-Assisted Direct Delivery of Genome Editing Machinery in Rice</i>
PS-46	Seema Choudhury , High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK) <i>Physics from Belle II experiment, status and prospects</i>
PS-47	Abin Sebastian , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), <i>Hydrogen peroxide evolution via Electrocatalytic Two-electron Water Oxidation by Zinc Porphyrin</i>

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Abstracts of Plenary and Invited Talks

Carbon Dots as Sustainable Materials for UV Screener, Direct White Light Emitter, and Laser

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Carbon dots (CDs) are futuristic materials for the rare-earth/toxic metal-free light emitting devices, bio imaging agents, as well as ecofriendly UV screeners [1,2]. The fluorescent CDs are composed mainly of C, O, H and they are attracting interest as they are readily synthesized by using soft and simple hydrothermal or solvothermal synthesis. They are synthesized at relatively low temperature with small energy consumption, as well as with completely metal-free and non-toxic reaction pathway compared to the inorganic phosphor materials. The emission property is tuned by the doping centre and surface functional groups leading to multi-coloured emission [1]. Our systematic investigation of the N-doping centres and surface functional groups have confirmed a vital role of the emission property [1]. The optimized synthetic strategy enabled us to tune the N doping sites and lead to the broadband emission, resulting in direct white light emission (WLE) in the entire visible spectra (400 to 750 nm). The decrease or increase of the N doping sites into the CDs led to the green to orange emission, respectively. The graphitic N creates mid-gap states within the HOMO-LUMO gap of the pristine CDs. As a result, the light absorption is red-shifted which gives rise to the low energy fluorescence in the visible spectrum. In this talk, we summarize our recent study on the development of luminescent carbon dots (CDs) for UV and high-energy blue light screener, direct white light emitter, as well as laser. An example of chromaticity tuning of *single-component* white light emitter by controlling the dopant types is demonstrated. Next, we also tried to enhance the light emission of CDs by combining with a planar microcavity structure with one or two resonant mode (s) coupled with the emission of the CDs and we observed sharp amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) and single-mode laser emission. These results contribute to the fundamental understanding of the structural and optical properties of CDs as well as developing novel CDs-based nano-photonics device, and can pave the way towards the development of completely rare-earth-free light emitting devices among other photonic devices.

Fig. 1. Laser emission at a wavelength matching the maximum emission of CDs. Inset shows the Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) of the DBR/CDs/DBR sample upon UV excitation as well as a photograph of the sample during the experiments.

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Earth system modeling for projecting the changing planet

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Global warming and related anthropogenic environmental changes are thought to cause severe extreme weather events, sea level rise, ocean acidification and deoxygenation, and large-scale ecosystem changes. The 6th phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6), an international program to simulate future changes in the global environment with Earth system models (ESMs), made significant contributions to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) published in August 2021. The MIROC series of ESMs developed by Japanese scientists also participated in CMIP6. In addition to CMIP6, new types of projection research, such as the development of models that incorporate the interactions between environmental change and socioeconomics, are also being actively pursued. This presentation will introduce various types of simulation models that contribute to the projection of global environmental changes, with some emphasis on the research by Indian and Japanese scientists. The current status of global environmental research being conducted within the framework of Japan-India cooperation will also be presented.

Aggregation Behavior of Polysaccharide Composite Particles and Application for Tissue Engineering

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Polysaccharides, which are abundant in nature, are attracting much attention as biomaterials. We have developed the methods to fabricate biomaterials from polysaccharides through formation of polyelectrolyte complex (PEC) of oppositely charged polysaccharides. One is the preparation of polysaccharide composite films by casting and drying of PEC particles dispersion obtained by mixing dilute polysaccharide solutions (Fig. 1 left) [1]. Furthermore, we found that polysaccharide PEC particles were aggregated by ions in a concentration-dependent manner. Their ability to aggregate polysaccharide PEC particles depended on the kinds of ions and followed the Hofmeister series. The chaotropic anion promoted more the aggregation of PIC particles than kosmotropic anion. Then, we attempted to fabricate hydrogels from polysaccharide PEC particle dispersion by utilizing the aggregation in the presence of ions and to culture three-dimensional cells therein. By adding phosphate buffered saline and cell suspension to the polysaccharide PEC particles dispersion composed of chondroitin sulfate C and chitosan, cells were loaded in the polysaccharide hydrogels with high viability (Fig. 1 center) [2]. Fabrication of cell scaffolds from polysaccharide PEC particles that can quickly gel are expected to be used as injectable cell scaffolds.

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Fig. 1 Preparation of biomaterials from polysaccharide composite particles

Plenary Talk

Fabrication and characterization of carrier-selective contact based silicon solar cells

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Energy harvesting from the sunlight has been one of the widely explored research areas with the built-in-potential creation from simple pn-junction followed by charge carrier collection. The present sole aim of the photovoltaic community is to explore low-cost solar cells and systems for harvesting abundant solar energy, and also to make the future energy production secure for global prosperity with the climate-neutral energy resources.

In case of solar cell fabrication to achieve the goal; the approach has been either by improving power conversion efficiency or by simple fabrication process steps. For high efficiency, silicon hetero-junction has shown the promise with amorphous silicon as a carrier selective layers. Under the low-cost process, recently, induced crystalline silicon pn-junction by the high/low work function metal oxides got an attention as carrier-selective contact (CSC) silicon solar cells.

This talk will focus on carrier-selective contact (CSC) based silicon solar cells fabrication by the above mentioned two approaches. The highest power conversion efficiency from the NiOx based CSC cells with simple process steps [1], and also room-temperature processed MoOx based CSC cells using low-cost silicon wafers [2, 3]. The carrier transport and interface recombination process at the carrier-selective junctions of these devices will be presented and explained during the talk [4, 5].

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Cell Surface Engineering with Biocompatible Polymers for Biomedical Applications

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The transplantation of therapeutic cells, tissue, and organs is an effective and fundamental treatment and has contributed to saving lives and improving quality of life. Because of the shortages, donated tissues and organs are carefully transplanted with the goal of retaining activity and viability. However, some issues remain to be resolved in terms of reducing side effects, improving graft survival, managing innate and adaptive immune responses, etc. We have tried to improve the graft survival by regulating innate immunity with our biomaterials (1,2) since the cell surface is exposed to immunological surveillance and reactions in recipient (3,4), we considered that the modulation of cell surface properties might improve transplantation outcomes. In particular, cell surface engineering with biocompatible polymers looks promising for this purpose. Here I will present the significance of polymer-based surface modification of cells and organs for transplantation therapy. In addition, I will also present other applications using cell surface engineering, cell manipulation and cell fusion. The cell manipulation is an important technique for delivery of therapeutic cells and their alignment for recellularization of decellularized tissues and organs in regenerative therapy. Also, the cell fusion is a fusion of different cells, which can lead to the formation of new functional cells that could be useful for generating e.g., immunologically competent or metabolically active cells. Thus, I will present three topics on cell surface engineering, which can contribute to the progress of biomedical applications.

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Magnetization Dynamics Study of High PMA Ultrathin Magnetic Heterostructures: A TRMOKE Study

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Ultra-thin ferromagnetic films with the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA) have been received a lot of attention for the spintronics application. Especially, spin transfer torque magnetoresistive random access memories (STT-MRAMs), consisting of arrays of magnetic tunneling junctions (MTJs), need the ultra-thin PMA film in order to increase the capacity. A recent critical issue of high-speed¹⁻³ and energy-efficient spintronic devices is coexistence of low magnetic Gilbert damping constant (α) and large PMA. Several kinds of ultra-thin ferromagnetic films were reported to have PMA, such as Fe¹, Co₂FeAl (CFA)², FeCo³ and CoFeB⁴. To continue such developmental process investigation of α as well as high PMA in the ultra-thin regime is extremely important. Here in this presentation we will discuss about two different high PMA ferromagnetic heterostructures (Fe/MAO and FeCo) with their damping analysis by time-resolved magneto-optical Kerr effect and discuss the origin of α based on the microstructure observation and the first principal calculation.

To clarify the spin-resolved contributions of low magnetic Gilbert damping constant and large perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA), a flat, lattice-matched interface has been developed in an Fe (0.7 nm)/MgAl₂O₄ (Oxide) (3 nm) bi-layer film by varying the *ex-situ* annealing temperature, which acts as a catalyst to vary the PMA energy densities according to the oxidation degree. The optimized procedure for interface engineering is implemented to achieve the lowest magnetic Gilbert damping constant (0.013) ever reported and a strong interfacial PMA energy (0.8 MJ m⁻³) for epitaxial thin films. By employing different interfacial atomic configurations in a first-principles calculation, this study explains the origin of the PMA energy and damping constant.

Tetragonally distorted FeCo alloys are other candidates for the ferromagnetic materials for STT-MRAM. Large PMA of 0.57 MJ/m³ was found for the ultra-thin FeCo sandwiched by Rh layers. To further investigate the potential of this material for the ferromagnetic layer in STT-MRAM, we have estimated α . We have found that 1.0 nm thick sample shows unusually high α value of 0.04. The detail microstructure observation shows the significant diffusion of Rh and the first principal calculation shows the inter-diffused Rh causes the increase in α . Judging from the large PMA and α , 1.0-nm-thick FeCo film is suitable for the reference layer in STT-MRAM.

Further, we got an interest in understanding of the damping behavior at elevated temperature for such high PMA FeCo alloys. We have developed the first ever high temperature TRMOKE microscope. A clear dynamical response of magnetization was observed at elevated temperature and the damping decreased with increasing sample temperature. A monotonic decrease of resonance frequency and damping constant as a function of temperature can be ascribed due to the extrinsic contribution mechanism. Thermal dependence of damping constant and effective anisotropic field, measured from this ferromagnetic methodology is very important for such highly anisotropic materials for the development of memory devices.

A detailed study of several spintronics materials will facilitate towards promising future spintronic applications.

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Can we predict the next pandemic?

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On the emergence of new pandemic world, a silent question is everywhere: Are we ready to predict the next pandemic and navigate an uncertain future? To answer this, we are researching ‘Silent Voice Sensing’ technologies to implement the ‘One Health’ concept, a crucial approach to preparing for future pandemics by recognizing the interconnections and early warning surveillance at the interface between humans, animals, and the shared environments. I will introduce our preparedness.

Novel Functional Organic Chromophores

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Porphyrins and other tetrapyrroles are highly suitable for sensing operations based on their synthetic flexibility and chromophore structures where an analyte might interact to stimulate some variation in directly observable optical colour or fluorescence emission modulation. Their chromophore structures also allow access to electronic triplet states, which can be harnessed for the generation of singlet oxygen – a highly reactive species useful for photodynamic action against tumours or microorganisms. Here we discuss the sensing activity of several β -substituted porphyrins¹ including not only by the introduction of suitable interacting units but also by the adaptation of non-planar porphyrins for the synthesis of porous structures. The latter are applied for film formation and sensing involving nanomechanical sensors. Selectivity and mechanisms of sensing activity are discussed. We will also introduce new efficient singlet oxygen generating materials based on agglomeration of an oxidized porphyrin chromophore as metal-organic frameworks,² electron deficient porous polymers, or using resorcinarenes.³ The use of these materials for selective oxidation of organic substrates is demonstrated. Overall, the results demonstrate the efficacy of the chromophore approach to functional materials. The self-assembly properties of porphyrins and nitrogen rich acene compounds, the pyrazinacenes, will also be considered based on contrasting cases of on-surface mobility and immobility, and the introduction of particular functionality influencing the resulting supramolecular structures.

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High Entropy Alloys for High Temperature Applications

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High entropy alloys (HEAs) have opened a vast alloy composition field for materials design, and some alloys have demonstrated excellent mechanical properties with reasonable ductility. In addition, lower mobility of alloying elements in the alloys could maintain microstructural stabilities and mechanical properties at elevated temperatures. Our research group have designed and evaluated some HEAs for high temperature applications, which are refractory high entropy alloys (RHEAs), platinum group metals based high entropy alloys (PGM-HEAs) and high entropy superalloys (HESAs) in collaboration with some universities overseas, such as National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan, Chalmers university of Technology, Sweden, and University of Bordeaux, France.

In this presentation, some research highlights in terms of HEAs designed for high temperature use are introduced, as following,

(i) Elemental Effect on oxidation resistance of RHEAs.

Effect of alloying elements on oxidation resistance of bcc-structured NbTi-rich RHEAs were investigated. For instance, Mo can enhance the oxidation behavior once the protective oxide layer which can resist the oxygen is diffused, due to its low oxygen solubility. On the other hand, Mo itself forms volatile oxides thereby presence of Mo on the surface would cause catastrophic damage to the alloys.

(ii) Development of Ni-rich HESAs with superior mechanical properties.

HESAs have been proposed to design alloy composition to lie in the high entropy field and to have coherent α and α' two-phase microstructure. Some alloys demonstrated higher yield stress with higher ductility at 750°C. Structure-property relationship will be discussed.

(iii) Development of PGM-HEAs

High temperature hardness and oxidation behavior of Ir-rich PGM-HEAs will be introduced. The designed Ir-rich PGM-HEAs possess FCC and L1₂ two phase structure and, interestingly, much improved oxidation resistance compared to conventional Ir-based alloys.

Plenary Talk

Electron microscopy techniques developed in NIMS for materials research

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Electron microscopes are widely used as standard microstructural evaluation tools in a wide range of research fields in science. Today, the functions of electron microscopes have been expanded and developed for many purposes, not only targeting high resolution but also by the objectives of applied research fields.

We have been studying microstructures using electron microscopy mainly for structural materials research, such as metals, alloys, steels, and ceramics. Most of the main needs for microstructure evaluation in this field are not only high-resolution, but other functions, such as accurate compositional analysis, three-dimensional(3D) morphological analysis, measurement of crystal orientation distribution, etc., have become more important. In our research group, we have developed such specific analytical techniques. While we apply both transmission electron microscope (TEM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM), One of SEM topics is introduced as follows as an example. TEM techniques will also be mentioned in the presentation.

Topic; 3D morphological observation by SEM

As most materials have 3-dimensional microstructure, and many of them are anisotropic, we must observe them in 3D for accurate evaluation. We have developed some serial-sectioning techniques based on a focused ion beam (FIB) -SEM for this purpose. One of them is an orthogonally arranged FIB-SEM to realize high contrast and resolution. The other is the large-scale 3D observation by Xe-plasma type FIB-SEM. By using these techniques, we can reach the argument on the mechanisms of mechanical properties.

Electron microscopes for 'open facility' in NIMS

We have been performing many joint research projects with researchers in many fields. In addition to joint research, NIMS has a framework to open many facilities, from material fabrication to characterization, to other researchers (mainly domestic). The system is called NIMS-open-facility. Under this formula, part of the electron microscopes in NIMS, from the versatile to the advanced ones, can be accessed.

Aakash project: toward clear air over the world

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The Research Institute for Humanity and Nature is a national research institute established by the Government of Japan in 2001. We, at RIHN, recognize that global environmental problems are common challenges for all humankind, and thus conduct research based on the foundations of various academic disciplines.

One of the full research projects currently underway at RIHN is the Aakash project. The name "aakash" means "sky" in Hindi. We named it with our wish for a blue sky in India that is so rare due to intense air pollution. The project aims at "An interdisciplinary study toward clean air, public health and sustainable agriculture: the case of crop residue burning in North India". The Aakash project focuses on air pollution caused by rice straw burning, a widespread practice in Northwest India. Every year from September to November is the rice harvest season, when tens of megatons of rice straw are burned in order to prepare field for the next cropping season in a short time. The air pollutants generated by straw burning are spread widely and are believed to cause severe air pollution in the surrounding areas, as far as the Delhi National Capital Region, affecting public health and well-being of many residents. To reduce the straw burning, we will pursue a pathway of social transformation toward clean air, public health and sustainable agriculture.

During the season of rice straw burning in this year, we measured air pollutants in the states of Punjab and Haryana using compact instruments with state-of-the-art technology. By comparing the measurements with the atmospheric model simulations, we will investigate the distribution of air pollutants generated by the rice straw burning, and chemical and physical processes of the pollutants. In the presentation, the latest results will be presented, including in-situ measurements by the small sensors and satellite remote sensing observations. Through this presentation, we hope you will understand that all of us humans live sharing one atmosphere.

Plenary Talk

Mechanisms at the level of atoms and electrons that drive electric field control over magnetism

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The ever-increasing demands of energy-efficient, faster and smaller electronics have triggered the quest for developing and understanding novel quantum phenomena with spintronics applications. In this direction, phenomena originating from the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) (*i.e.* the relativistic interaction between the electronic spin and momentum degrees of freedom), like non-collinear magnetism, perpendicular magnetic anisotropy, spin-momentum locking and spin-orbit torque and topological non-trivial phenomena, are at the forefront of our research activities at Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan. We are also interested in exploring the prospect of the electric field control of these functionalities, which is one of the defining features of the future ultra-low energy memory applications. One of the major objectives of our endeavors is to develop an understanding of the mechanisms at the level of atoms and electrons which leads to the emergence of unique SOC properties. Our research activities are also focused on developing guidelines to control and optimize various SOC properties in real materials.

Here, we will discuss the mechanisms of cross-coupling between ferroelectricity and magnetism in the context of complex oxides. Ferroelectric (FE) materials, which exhibit spontaneous electric polarization, switchable by electric field (\mathbf{E}), create promising environments to develop control of \mathbf{E} over magnetism, *i.e.* magnetoelectric (ME) coupling. Recently, we have investigated and proposed strong magnetization (\mathbf{M}) and ME coupling which is expected to be functional at room temperature in certain hexagonal phase of transition metal oxides (Nat. Commun. **5**, 2998 (2014), Nat. Mater. **13**, 163 (2014), Nature **537**, 523 (2016), Nat. Commun. **11**, 5582 (2020)). Based on the coupling between the magnetic interactions and the FE order parameters observed in these systems, microscopic mechanisms to achieve \mathbf{E} induced spin-reorientation transitions and 180° switching of the direction of \mathbf{M} will be discussed.

Invited Talk

High temperature materials: Ni-based superalloys and beyond

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High temperature structural materials have significantly improved the performance of aircraft jet engines and land-based gas turbine engines. Due to their excellent high temperature strength and corrosion resistance, Ni-based superalloys have been selected as a material for the hottest section. The temperature capability of Ni-based superalloys has been improved over 70 years, enabling the operating temperature to increase up to 1100 °C. The deformation of Ni-based superalloys is dominated by γ' -shearing event accompanied by the formation of planar defects. Recent studies revealed that the segregation of certain elements to planar defects could improve the creep resistance by locally changing the crystal structure and compositions of planar defects, thereby decreasing their stacking fault energy and preventing microtwinning (Local Phase Transformation Strengthening, LPTS). While the correlation between the composition dependence and activated deformation mechanisms in Ni-based superalloys has been actively investigated to further increase their temperature capability, we explore the design of a new class of refractory metal-based alloys that can survive in the environment exceeding the current temperature limit of advanced Ni-based superalloys. Our recent findings of the composition dependence on hardness and creep resistance, and the effect of solute segregation will be presented. Potential candidate alloys and the design strategy to meet the requirements as a next-generation high temperature material will be introduced.

Hybrid of experiment and computation for the interpretation of biomolecular sequence and structural data

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Biological science now thrives on information. The classical problems are currently solved in a data-driven way. One such problem is to derive structure of biomolecules using experiments which are not originally meant to be used in structure determination. For example, atomic force microscopy, once a technique to study surface characteristics of materials, is now also used to study biomolecular conformation in a 2D plane. Computational techniques are now used on top of that to obtain 3D structural information. This adds to the interpretation of dynamic characteristics of biomolecules – a perfect marriage between wet-lab and dry-lab experiments. Another data-intensive problem is to interpret biological high-throughput sequence data, for example, interpretation of data obtained from third-generation sequencer, Oxford nanopore. Here, a nucleotide is passed through a membrane-embedded channel protein and change in the ionic gradient is measured as a 1D signal. A translation of the 1D signal to biological 4-letter sequence is done by the use of artificial neural network-based inference. However, in some cases such translations are obscured by aberrant chemical modifications of the nucleotides, particularly for RNA – studied in ‘epitranscriptomics’. As those base-modifications are related to diseases like cancer and neurodegeneration, a detector of the modification is heavily demanded. This problem is entirely solved by machine-learning models – another example of blending computation and experiment. In summary, the future technology should be such that it wouldn’t matter whether the experiment is dry or wet and only the evidence of the result speaks for itself.

Plenary Talk

Electrochromic Metallo-Supramolecular Polymers

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Electrically controlled dimming window, what is called smart window, is expected to contribute to energy-saving of air-conditioning in office buildings or vehicles because of the controlled sunlight shading.

Among several driving systems of smart window an electrochromic device (ECD) is a promising one and ECDs with viologen as an EC material have been installed as the windows of Boeing 787. However, the further development of EC materials is required to the wide commercialization.

We have developed metallo-supramolecular polymers with EC properties. The novel EC materials have been found to have much better EC properties than the conventional materials. In my presentation the EC properties and the ECD fabrication will be introduced.

Smart Hydrogels with Excellent Swelling and Mechanical Properties for Realistic Medical Simulators

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With advances in medical technology, the use of minimally invasive surgery is rapidly increasing, and minimally invasive techniques are becoming a standard surgical technique. The devices for technique training available on the market are made of dry materials such as silicone and soft urethane, which have a texture far removed from that of living tissue, and the materials themselves are expensive and impose significant running costs and environmental burdens. The purpose of this study is to establish and put into practical use a technology to provide a simulator for procedural training that is as close to living tissue as possible using hydrogel, prepared by a simple process and at low cost.

Among hydrogels, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) gel has excellent mechanical properties, water retention, and high biocompatibility. In the last decade, the development of sample preparation techniques, especially in the field of biomedical engineering, has attracted much attention.^{1,2)} In this talk, we will present a preparation method for preparing transparent PVA gels with excellent swelling and mechanical properties by a non-freezing isothermal crystallization method. As a result of studying the optimum conditions for gel preparation, we are now able to prepare gels with high swelling rate and mechanical strength and different transparency. By combining the present results with our recent gelation techniques¹⁻⁵⁾, we will discuss the development of medical devices such as artificial organ phantoms and surgical training models using PVA hydrogels.

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Electrochemical Biosensors

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Biosensors are analytical devices that incorporates bio-recognition elements such as receptors, organelles or engineered proteins and employed often for the quantification of biological/bio-chemical process. Based on the transduction mode, biosensors are classified in to several types such as electrochemical biosensors, optical biosensors, magnetic biosensors etc. Of various known biosensors, electrochemical biosensors offer excellent sensitivity, selectivity, rapid response time, high signal-to-noise ratio and the possibility of multiplexed detection. Recent advancements in the development of functional materials enabled the construction of novel electrochemical transduction platforms for a variety of biosensing applications. In this presentation, the usefulness of some interesting carbon and other 2D materials for biosensing applications will be discussed.

Plenary Talk

Orexin, sleep, and narcolepsy; The discovery received the 2023 “Breakthrough Prize”

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Narcolepsy-cataplexy is a chronic neurological disorder associated with excessive daytime sleepiness, sleep attacks, cataplexy, sleep paralysis, hypnagogic hallucinations, and fragmentation of nighttime sleep. The discovery of orexin (hypocretin) by two groups simultaneously and independently revolutionized the field of sleep and narcolepsy research. It was found that the loss of orexin-producing neurons, which are seated almost exclusively in the lateral hypothalamus, is responsible for narcolepsy and sleep/wake disturbances. Since the discovery of orexin in 1998, orexin has been implicated in several physiological processes such as feeding, energy metabolism, reward, and addiction. Our goal is to elucidate the neural and molecular mechanism involved in orexin-mediated sleep/wake and the pathology of narcolepsy. Currently, only symptomatic treatment is available for narcolepsy/cataplexy. Here we demonstrate that the narcoleptic symptoms of orexin knockout mice can be reversed by lumbar-level intrathecal orexin delivery. The cataplexy and sleep-onset REM sleep (SOREM) were decreased in narcolepsy model mice during slow infusion of orexin. Next, we studied the chronic effects of suvorexant, an orexin receptor antagonist, approved to treat insomnia in human patients. We found that chronic use of orexin antagonists can change the brain architecture similar to a narcolepsy mouse model, and in a high dose it can be cataplectic if administered with positive emotions in a stress-free condition. Additionally, we reported that both physical and psychological stress inhibits the occurrence of narcolepsy. While orexin agonists/antagonists could prove vital to treat several neurological disorders, our study warrants their cautious use with co-morbid disorders.

Invited Talk

Multi-Therapeutic Applications of Engineered Phage Capsids

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We highlight the development of bacteriophage capsid-based gene/chemo/vaccine delivery system relevant for in vitro therapeutic applications and envision well-characterized, safety-approved phages through modular genetic engineering technologies. This presentation will focus on the manipulation of the inherent abilities of bacteriophages (a very common co-existing organism in the human body) for efficient mammalian cell targeted delivery applications, focusing on 1. chemotherapeutics for cancer therapy, 2. antigen display for bacterial disease prevention (vaccine) and 3. gene delivery for treating metabolic disorder. The methodology includes deletion of non-desired functional genes, modification of existing phage genes (by phage display) and incorporation of additional payloads (genes/antigens/chemotherapeutic drugs). We summarize the results of the successful testing of the efficacy of these phage capsid delivery systems in vitro using cancer and immune mammalian cell types.

Invited Talk

Nanostructured photoelectrochemical platform probing visible light-driven virus detection

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The characterization of the photoinduced carriers' production, separation, and interfacial reaction processes is critical in developing effective photoelectrochemical (PEC) detection. The design and fabrication of a visiblelight-driven PEC device based on CdSe-Co₃O₄@TiO₂ nanoflower are presented in this report. In addition, an application for the ultrasensitive detection of viruses, including hepatitis E virus (HEV), HEV-like particles (HEV-LPs), and SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in complex lysate solution. The photocurrent response output of a CdSe-Co₃O₄@TiO₂ based PEC device is improved compared to the individual components, TiO₂ and CdSe@Co₃O₄. This can be ascribed to forming a heterojunction structure obtained by the hybridization of TiO₂ and CdSe-Co₃O₄. CdSe QDs sensitization effect and strong visible light absorption can extend interfacial carrier lifetime and enhance energy conversion efficiency coupling with a robust oxygen-evolving catalyst (Co₃O₄) at the hole trapping site (CdSe) to improve overall system stability. The developed PEC-based biosensing device has been effectively used for quantitative virus detection through effective hybridization among antibody and viral specimens. The effective capture of the virus resulted in a linear relationship of change in photocurrent output versus the HEV concentration ranging from 10 fg mL⁻¹ to 100 ng mL⁻¹ with a detection limit of 3.5 fg mL⁻¹. This CdSe-Co₃O₄@TiO₂ -based PEC device shows a significant ability to develop an improved device with affordable and portable biosensing capabilities.

Coadditive Engineering for Stable Sn-based perovskite solar cells

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Recently, Sn-based perovskites have been considered as promising photovoltaic materials due to their low-toxicity and optimum optoelectronic properties. But uncontrolled crystallization and facial Sn²⁺ oxidation, make performance and long-term stability for Sn-based perovskite solar cells (PSCs) more challenging [1,2]. Here, we present a coadditive engineering with hydrazinium chloride and 5-ammonium valeric acid iodide for Sn-based PSCs [3,4]. From detail characterization, we observed that the coadditive engineering helped to control growth rate and to assist vertical crystallization of perovskite film. On the other hand, the compositional engineering optimized the energy level with the corresponding charge selective layer and impart stability. These positive aspects of this process made us able to boost the power conversion efficiency over 8%. More importantly, the high performing PSCs maintained their 85% initial PCE under light soaking condition for 1000 h.

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Probing chemical reaction dynamics through excited-state time-dependent *GW* simulations

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Understanding the mechanisms behind chemical reactions is an important step towards understanding the world we live in and also designing new materials for applications that enhance our lives. The dynamics of such reactions can be understood either via (a) experimental or (b) computational efforts. The second route falls into the domain of computational materials science which broadly deals with the study of materials and their properties by means of computer codes based on rigorous mathematical principles. This has been a rapidly growing area owing to the availability of a wide spectrum of formalisms, corresponding computer codes, as well as powerful computing resources. Density functional theory (DFT) [1] is one such theory in this area, which has been applied extensively and successfully, to understand materials and their ground state properties at the atomistic level [1]. Despite its versatility, DFT is plagued with some major issues [1] which can be a roadblock when attempting at understanding the dynamics of chemical reactions via its time-dependent (TD) extension, TDDFT. The *GW* method is one such method that mitigates to a large extent, these severe problems of DFT [2]. It has been shown to be a computationally formidable theory [2] and as a result, its time-dependent (TD) extension, TD*GW*, has never been attempted before to obtain accurate dynamics. More recently, we have demonstrated through its efficient implementation in our home-grown code, Tohoku mixed basis orbitals (TOMBO) *ab initio* program [3], how this theory scales linearly with the system size as well as computational resources [4]. Encouraged by this, we perform for the first time the TD*GW* simulation of a bond dissociation process in a simple system, the Methane (CH₄) molecule. In this talk, I will present our preliminary results and also demonstrate how TD*GW* accurately predicts this bond dissociation process in a reasonable walltime of the simulation. We expect this preliminary success of TD*GW* to spawn more explorations into the dynamics of reactions in larger systems in the future.

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Abstracts of Poster Presentation

Glassy Phase in Dense Bacteria Population

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A glassy phase refers to an amorphous state of the material wherein the structural and orientational order is absent. The transition resulting in such a material phase is widely known as the *glass transition*. More specifically, the glass transition is a non-equilibrium phase transition wherein the system in a liquid state attains a kinetically arrested amorphous state on cooling or increasing the density of its constituents. The dynamical slowdown, high viscosity, fragility, and dynamical heterogeneity are some of the key signatures of glass transition. Recently, we found that the dense population of bacteria growing in a confined microfluidic device exhibits the glass transition phenomenon and displays key signatures of glass. We believe that such investigation of microorganisms from the lens of material science will allow us the understand dense state of bacteria such as biofilm and the associated complex biophysical process.

Multinational advancements for AI-driven road inspection

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Road safety has continued to be a pressing concern, with road traffic accidents being a global disaster hampering the life of millions. Poor road conditions are one of the major factors leading to road accidents. Apropos, there is an immediate need for fresh inventions and an uphill trajectory in technology to reform the road and transportation arena.

The talk addresses the status quo of research efforts in the domain of AI (Artificial Intelligence)-driven road condition inspection (Figure 1). Advancements for multiple countries are covered based on research outcomes for India, Japan, the Czech Republic, the United States, Norway, and China. The underlying research study encapsulates deep learning-based methods for automatic road damage detection. Data in the form of road images captured using smartphones, high-resolution cameras, drones, google street view images, etc., is utilized to carry out the analysis for real-time applications. The main feature of the study is to investigate the transferability of solutions developed for one country to address the same problem in other countries. Additionally, the involvement of the public in implementing the proposed solution at a larger scale through the release of a Smartphone-App is analyzed.

Figure 1: AI-driven automation enables Smartphone-based low-cost, quick road condition monitoring, overcoming the limitation of traditional approaches involving manual inspection.

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Violet light modulates mood behavior via non-visual retinal opsin OPN5

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Depression is the second greatest cause of clinical problems that result in poor quality of life, including sleep, cognitive impairment, and mortality. Antidepressants now on the market have a 40–50% success rate in treating depression with a delayed onset of effect. Unfortunately, their treatment and prevention of depression continue to be difficult. In the central nervous system (CNS), the oligodendrocyte-formed myelin sheath is one of the major components for normal neuronal functioning in depression. The oligodendrocytes, one of the main glial cell types create the distinctive, lipid-rich myelin membrane that forms multilamellar spiral sheaths around neuronal axons in the central nervous system. A disruption in oligodendrocyte functions results in neurological deficits, such as depression and multiple sclerosis (MS) and ultimately leads to severe brain damage.

Violet light (VL, 360-400nm wavelength) has recently been found to activate the OPN5 photoreceptor, which is critical for both eye and brain function. Preliminary sequencing results in aged mice demonstrate that VL enhances transcription of genes involved in neural myelination, implying that VL may have an effect on memory performance. To assess the efficacy of VL as a potential light therapy to improve mood behavior via OPN5, we looked at the effect of VL exposure in a social defeat stress (SDS) depression model. The results demonstrated that VL irradiation has no effect on brain function and behavior in OPN5 KO (whole body) compared to wild type animals and conclude that OPN5(+) RGCs in the retina are responsible for conveying light stimulation of the VL to the brain (Fig 1). Interestingly, when compared to white light (WL)-exposed defeated mice, VL dramatically enhanced myelination. VL has a substantial effect as a novel non-invasive treatment for mood disorders. The findings highlight the importance of the OPN5 function controlled by VL as a novel target in the treatment of depressive-like behaviors.

Nafion's Proton Transport in Cathode Catalyst Layer of Hydrogen Fuel Cell

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The hydrogen fuel cell performance is largely determined at cathode catalyst layer where thin ionomer film binds with platinum coated carbon particles (Pt/C) in spatial heterogeneous manner. Since the ionic mobility of ionomer thin-film is greatly affected by the thickness of ionomer, and connectivity with different substrates, it is important to quantitatively estimate the proton conductivity of Nafion thin film on C and Pt substrates. Therefore, we are developing planar interdigitated electrodes (IDEs) with C, Pt and quartz substrates to measure the proton (H^+) transport in Nafion thin film using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Pt IDEs with quartz (Pt-Q IDE), carbon (Pt-C IDE) and platinum (Pt-Pt IDE) surfaces (Fig. 1(a – c)) were fabricated in clean room facilities. The 1.2wt% Nafion dispersion was spin coated and Nafion films were dried overnight at 40°C under vacuum before EIS measurement in N_2 and 5% H_2 environment. Relative humidity (RH) dependence of in-plane H^+ transport resistance was obtained and discussed through EIS measurements.

The thickness of Nafion films was kept uniform at ~55 nm. Fig. 1 (d) shows the H^+ conductivity at quartz substrate, and 1(e) shows H^+ conductivity at carbon and platinum substrates respectively. The H^+ conductivity was estimated by different impedance components based on Ionomer/substrate interfacial area in the IDEs. The quantitative attribution of H^+ transport on three surfaces will be discussed in detail at the conference site. In conclusion, H^+ conductivity at carbon and platinum substrate was found to be approximately one-order higher than that at quartz substrate.

Figure 1. (a – c) Cross sectional view of Pt IDEs. (d) H^+ conductivity at quartz substrate. (e) H^+ conductivity at carbon and platinum.

Modification of extracellular vesicles with oligopeptide for selective interaction with activated endothelium

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Introduction: Exosome (diameter 30-150 nm), a subtype of extracellular vesicles containing DNA, miRNA, protein inside [1]. Therefore, exosomes are expected to carry drugs or functional miRNA for disease treatment. In fact, treatment by exosome could attenuate ischemia in mice model [2]. However, the delivery of exosome was not specific and had short clearance time even though exosome has intrinsic delivery functions and minimal reaction to innate immune system. There is a possibility that surface modification of exosome with specific functional peptides improve the delivery efficiency of exosome and prolong the clearance time in vivo. We focused on E-selectin, a cell adhesion molecule and highly expressed on the surface of endothelial cells in response to inflammation during stroke. So far, we reported the conjugation of E-selectin binding peptide (Esbp) with poly (ethylene glycol)-conjugated phospholipid (PEG-lipid) for the cell surface modification [3]. Here we aimed to modify the exosome surface with Esbp-PEG-lipid for inducing selective interaction with activated endothelium in vitro.

Results and discussion: Maleimide-PEG-lipid was synthesized as previously reported [3], and then was conjugated with Esbp (DITWDQLWDLMKGGGC) by thiol-maleimide reaction. Human embryonic kidney 293T cells were cultured until 80% confluence and the exosome was isolated from conditioned medium by centrifugation and Total exosome isolation reagent. Exosome size and representative surface markers were characterized by Western blot and Nanosight. Then, exosome was treated by different types of Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-labeled Esbp-PEG-lipid and number of FITC-Esbp-PEG-lipid per an exosome was estimated by fluorospectrophotometer. Interaction of modified exosome with E-selectin was analyzed by Quartz Crystal Microbalance with Dissipation, indicating that Esbp-PEG-lipid modified exosome had significantly higher binding to E-selectin than control groups.

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Influences of yttrium micro-addition on microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of IN718 fabricated by selective laser melting.

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The influence of yttrium (Y) addition on the microstructures and high-temperature mechanical properties of Inconel718 have been investigated. In this study, alloys containing 0.07% , 0.58% of Y and base alloy without Y were fabricated using the selective laser melting method and a solution, aging heat treatments (STA) were conducted. The mechanical properties were evaluated by high-temperature tensile and creep tests at 650 °C. The results shown in fig.1 reveals that the lower Y addition (0.07Y) enhanced the tensile ductility with no significant change in the strength. Further, the creep rupture life and ductility were also improved. The superior high temperature ductility in lower Y-added alloy is mainly attributed to the grain boundary segregation of Y, which led to the morphological change of the δ phase precipitates and to the stabilization of oxygen by the formation of Y_2O_3 at grain boundaries (fig.2). However, the beneficial effect of Y on ductility was suppressed when Y content was 0.58%. The higher Y-added alloy showed a sharp decreased in ductility, when compared to the lower Y-added alloy, owing to the intense precipitation of brittle Y-rich Ni_5Y and NbC phases at intergranular and interdendritic regions.

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of STA specimens with various Y additions: (a), 0Y, (b) 0.07Y; and (c) 0.58Y.

Fig. 2. Effect of Y on the (a) tensile and (b) creep properties of STA specimens at 650 °C.

Experimental evidence to the anti-migration activity of Cucurbitacin-B

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Cancer metastasis, a highly complex transformation of cancer cells, is mostly treated with synthetic chemotherapeutic molecules that are known to cause severe adverse effects and are very expensive. Natural compounds, on the other hand, are considered safe, easily available and economic. We have earlier reported anticancer potential of a combination of Cucurbitacin (Cuc)-B and Withanone (Wi-N), called CucWi-N. Cancer cells treated with CucWi-N showed induction of cellular senescence and decrease in migration. Both Cuc-B and Wi-N are known to possess anticancer potential, their combination CucWi-N was shown to offer better anticancer activity. Molecular dynamics analyses of Cuc-B interaction with two proteins (Mortalin and HDM2) that are enriched in cancer cells, negatively regulate p53 and promote cancer cell migration supported that it has ability to disrupt mortalin-p53 interaction yielding nuclear translocation and activation of wild type p53 function. Cuc-B was seen to interact with HDM2 like its known inhibitor Y30. Furthermore, downregulation of mortalin, MMP-3 and hnRNP-K proteins that are critically involved in cell migration was observed suggesting that Cuc-B is a potential natural drug that warrants further mechanistic and clinical studies for its use in management of metastatic cancers.

PS-8

A novel small molecule that inhibits proliferation and migration of cancer cells

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Mortalin, a member of the Hsp70 family of proteins, is enriched in many types of cancers. It has been shown to promote the process of carcinogenesis by multiple ways. Cancer cells compromised for mortalin expression or lacking mortalin-p53 (a major tumor suppressor protein) interaction show growth arrest/apoptosis. Based on these mortalin inhibitors have been proposed to possess anticancer activity. In this context, screening of a chemical library to identify potential abrogators of mortalin-p53 interaction was performed, and two novel synthetic small molecules were isolated. Molecular analyses revealed that these compounds target Mortalin and PARP1 (hence called called Mortaparib and Mortaparib^{Plus}) through targeting mortalin and PARP1 proteins. We report a similar compound with milder activity (hence called Mortaparib^{Mild}) as a potential anticancer compound. Cancer cells possessing wild type, mutant or null p53 status subjected to Mortaparib^{Mild} treatment showed inhibition of cell proliferation, migration and invasion capacity that is mediated by multiple pathways. Taken together, we report the anticancer small molecule that warrants further attention in laboratory and clinical studies.

***In vitro* experimental evidence to the anti-stress activity in a popular carotenoid fucoxanthin**

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Stress is an inevitable component of life and has been connected to the poor quality of life, especially towards later years of human lifespan when there is a decrease in efficiency of damage-repair processes. Recruitment of natural compounds for stress management is expected to decrease the disease burden and hence benefit the health care system. Fucoxanthin is a popular carotenoid found in marine organisms and known for its antioxidant and cytoprotective capacities. In this study, we examined the antistress potential of fucoxanthin using *in vitro* cell-based assays. Cultured cells were subjected to extrinsic stresses (UV, oxidative stress, heavy metal, heat stress) and intrinsic stresses (a replicative senescence-based physiologically relevant stress model developed by a serial passaging of human lung fibroblast), followed by recovery either in the normal or fucoxanthin supplemented medium. Phenotypic and molecular analyses of control, stressed (with or without fucoxanthin) cells showed that fucoxanthin offered protection against the extrinsic stress induced cytotoxicity and cellular protein aggregation. Besides, the replicative senescent model revealed decreased cell viability, accumulation of DNA damage and oxidative stress in the old vs young fibroblasts, which was significantly rescued by fucoxanthin. Furthermore, in a unique genetic model of amyloid beta aggregation (an established causative factor of Alzheimer's disease), fucoxanthin was seen to cause deaggregation of beta-amyloid yielding protection against beta-amyloid induced cytotoxicity. Taken together, these results demonstrated antistress potentials of fucoxanthin that may be useful for management of stress and old-age related pathologies.

Multi-Responsive Star-Shaped Porphyrin-PNIPAM Conjugates

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Star-shaped porphyrin-PNIPAM (**PP**) conjugates with four PNIPAM arms connected to a central porphyrin unit were synthesized using RAFT polymerization¹ (Fig. 1a). Temperature-induced phase separation (Fig. 1b,c) behaviour of **PP** was investigated, and the LCST (type II) phase diagram was constructed using Flory–Huggins theory. Below phase-separation temperature (T_p), **PP** behaves as a 1D supramolecular polymer with a concentration-dependent length, while above T_p , **PP** adopts larger spherical globular structures (Fig. 1b). Various temperature–pH reversible and irreversible interdependencies (“cross-effects”) between phase separation and protonation were observed by NMR^{2,3}, DSC, SAXS, DLS and UV-Vis.

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of **PP** (only one arm is shown). (b) Illustration of temperature (ΔT) or pH (ΔpH) change on an aqueous solution of **PP**. Vials are irradiated with a green laser pointer (532 nm). (c) Two-state model of phase separation^{2,3} fitted to NMR data.

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Environmental improvements from alternative gravel mounts in channelized rivers

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The ecological environment inside channelized rivers is generally poor as the flow is too uniform and fast for most aquatic species. These conditions get worse during flood stages when the water volume exceeds the swim capacity of fishes and the cross section becomes unliveable. To improve the current situation, several river restoration strategies are researched and applied in the field. Our research focuses on the potential environmental improvements thanks to the installation of alternative gravel mounts with stacked boulders reinforcement inside channelized rivers. Physical models are characterized by seven gravel mounts built on alternative sides of the channel above the gravel bed ($d_{50}=0.017\text{m}$, homogenous). Each mount is triangular and its shape is reinforced by two layers of stacked boulders placed like fallen dominoes on each other's ($D_{50}=0.063\text{m}$, homogeneous). Further two layers of stacked boulders are placed along both sides of the channel to stabilize the water surface. The habitat requirements for Ayu Sweetfishes (*Plecoglossus altivelis*) are mathematically modelled as everywhere inside the flow field where time-averaged flow velocity $V \leq 0.1\text{m/s}$ and standard deviation of the velocity $\text{std}(V) \leq 0.07\text{m/s}$. The empty spaces generated between the stacked boulders are investigated as possible refuge areas where the target species might find refuge from the main flow's force, as the discharge is set at the maximal capacity of the experimental channel. The results gathered so far are very satisfying: there is clear increase of the flow heterogeneity and the time-averaged flow velocity reduces near the gravel surface. The water surface along the sides of the channel is flat thanks to the stacked boulders installed there. Based on the defined thresholds, every gravel mounts appear to be able to generate in its own shadow a suitable volume half its own. The simplicity of model's design and materials is also positive aspects of this research. The observed rise of average water surface is less than optimal, because it means a reduction in the cross-sectional capacity, but not troubling, as the effect can be balanced by lowering the bed. Finally, experiments with living fishes have highlighted the possibility of refuge inside the stacked boulders constructions. Future research will investigate the environmental benefits that gravel mounts could bring during times of regular flow. The investigation of dead zones (areas with virtually no water movement and therefore a suitable environment for microorganisms and fish spawning) will be important.

Development of Multiferroic BiFeO₃ based Thin Films with Excellent Magnetic Properties for Reduction of Energy Consumption in Magnetic Devices

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Present magnetic devices are operated by magnetic field or spin current, where energy consumption is high. Very low energy consumption can be achieved by using the multiferroic materials with ferroelectricity and ferromagnetism instead of typical magnetic materials, where we can control magnetization by applying electric field. Bismuth Ferrite (BiFeO₃(BFO)) is a promising multiferroic material in room temperature. But it shows an antiferromagnetic (G-type) configuration. The antiferromagnetic property of pure BFO needs to be changed to ferrimagnetic property by substitution with Bi and/or Fe. In general, multiferroic materials do not have high saturation magnetization (M_s), high magnetic Kerr rotation angle (Θ_k), high perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (ratio of perpendicular coercivity against in-plane coercivity; $H_{c\perp}/H_{c\parallel}$), and high Curie temperature (T_C). Therefore, improvement of above properties are important for magnetic device applications. In our previous study, we found improvement in M_s of relatively 95 emu/cm³ in (Bi,Ba)(Fe,Co)O₃ film by substituting Ba as A-site substituent and Co as B-site substituent, but the and $H_{c\perp}/H_{c\parallel}$ of 1.1 and Θ_k of 0.20° were not sufficient for device applications. In this study, we investigated the improvement of magnetic properties like M_s , $H_{c\perp}/H_{c\parallel}$, Θ_k and T_C in (Bi,L)(Fe,Co)O₃ (L: Lanthanides) films by substituting different Lanthanides. Here, from previous study, concentration of Lanthanides in A-site is fixed at around 40-60 at% and the concentration of Co in B-site is optimized to 25 at% to obtain good magnetic properties in (Bi,L)(Fe,Co)O₃ films.

The highest M_s of 140 emu/cm³ and large perpendicular magnetic anisotropy ($H_{c\perp}/H_{c\parallel}$ of 2.6) were found in (Bi,Nd)(Fe,Co)O₃ film, and maximum Θ_k of 0.67° and relatively high $H_{c\perp}/H_{c\parallel}$ of 1.6 were found in (Bi,La)(Fe,Co)O₃ film. These properties are suitable for magnetic recording devices and optical devices respectively. A very small coercivity of 0.8 kOe along with high M_s of 110 emu/cm³ and T_C of 450 °C respectively were observed in (Bi,Eu)(Fe,Co)O₃ film. So, (Bi,Eu)(Fe,Co)O₃ film is suitable for magnetic sensor applications because of its high sensitivity to magnetic fields.

Therefore, suitable Lanthanoid substitution in A-site is also key factor to obtain good magnetic properties in BFO films for magnetic device applications.

Manipulation of liposome by spontaneous incorporation of cell-penetrating peptide

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The use of amphiphilic molecules such as poly(ethylene glycol)-conjugated phospholipid (PEG-lipid) enables the incorporation into liposome surfaces by the self-assembly with lipids¹⁾. This technique can be applied for the manipulation of both living cells²⁾ and liposomes³⁾. Here we aimed to characterize Tat peptide (YGRKKRRQRRR)-conjugated PEG-lipids for liposomes (size: ca. 100 nm). We synthesized different types of Tat-PEG-lipids by combining PEG of different molecular weights (5 kDa and 40 kDa) with different lipids with three acyl chains (myristoyl, palmitoyl, and stearoyl, respectively). Two types of cell-penetrating peptide (Tat: YGRKKRRQRRRGGGGC, Tat-Col: YGRKK RRQRRRGGGGPPGVVGEQGEQGPPGGGC) were conjugated to PEG-lipids. Here, a collagenase cleavage site was inserted as a Col. Those PEG-lipid conjugates were incorporated into the surface of the fluorescently labeled liposome and seeded on a glass substrate. Then, the amount of liposome adsorption was quantitatively analyzed. In addition, liposomes modified with Tat-Col-PEG-lipids were seeded and then treated with collagenase to cleave the peptide site to examine the detachment of the liposomes.

We observed the spontaneous adsorption of liposomes by Tat peptide onto the substrate surface by mixing Tat-PEG-lipid or Tat-Col-PEG-lipid with liposomes. The adsorption of liposome increased with a decrease of PEG chain and acyl chain length in Tat-PEG-lipid. The difference in the adsorption amount was due to the difference in the incorporated amount of Tat-PEG-lipid into the liposome surface. Also, the liposome desorption rate was increased with a decrease of acyl chain length of the lipid. Thus, Tat-PEG-lipid can be a suitable tool for the manipulation of liposomes and cells.

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Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4Zr-4Nb alloys fabricated by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS)

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【Introduction】 Near- α titanium alloys are used for fan blades and compressor components due to their light weight, excellent strength and other corrosion resistance at high temperatures [1]. Forging and rolling are the most selected manufacturing processes, however, conventional forging and rolling processes often developed nonuniform microstructure and generated a significant amount of material waste due to machining after the process. Recently powder metallurgy methods such as Selective Laser Melting (SLM) and Electron Beam Melting (EBM) have been introduced as attractive new manufacturing processes. In these processes, powder is melted and rapidly solidified by laser or electron beam, which enables us to remove the machining process, thereby reducing the materials waste [2]. Previously, Kuroda et al [3] has investigated the microstructure and high-temperature mechanical properties of Ti alloys fabricated by SLM and found they contained pores, which formed during melting process, caused the decrease of creep rupture life. Therefore, in this study, we focus on the SPS method to fabricate the denser material with less pores. The microstructure and mechanical properties were evaluated and compared to materials fabricated by SPS, forging, and SLM.

【Experimental】 The samples were prepared by SPS using Ti-6Al-4Nb-4Zr (wt%) powder (manufactured by TANIOBIS), which has excellent oxidation resistance and has been developed at the National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS). The samples were sintered at 800, 900, 950, 1100, and 1200°C in an Ar atmosphere under a pressure of 90 MPa. Microstructure characterization was carried out using JSM-7200F scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). Compression tests at room and elevated temperatures, and creep tests were performed to evaluate the mechanical properties.

【Result】 The obtained microstructure significantly varied for the sintered temperature. In the $\alpha + \beta$ two-phase temperature region, slow cooling led to the formation of an $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure with equiaxed α phase and β phase surrounding them. On the other hand, when sintered above β -transus temperatures, the α/β lamellar structure formed in the grains with 100 μm in size. The grain size in SPS samples was smaller than those of the forged samples with 500 μm in size.

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Graphitic carbon nitride-based nanoplatfoms for environmental applications: design strategies and applications

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Semiconductor photocatalytic technology has become one of the most important means to solve the current energy shortage and environmental pollution. Compared with the traditional photocatalysts, graphite carbon nitride has a wider range of light-harvesting and more stable physical and chemical properties. However, traditional thermally induced polymerization of nitrogen-containing precursors produces melon-based carbon nitride solids with an amorphous or semi-crystalline structure, resulting in low conductivity and moderate photocatalytic activity. Recently, low band gap carbon nitrides (g-C₃N₅) have attracted more and more attention in improving photocatalytic performance. Some significant progress regarding crystalline carbon nitride for the preparation of solar-fuel and environmental purification has also been made. The work primarily focused on the design and synthesis of g-C₃N₅ photocatalysts. The photocatalytic application of g-C₃N₅ was studied, mainly including photocatalytic H₂ production, photocatalytic and photocatalytic degradation of pollutants. The process is a sustainable and efficient treatment of wastewater with controllable and active photocatalyst and can be considered as an environment friendly technique for environmental remediation.

Keywords: Carbon nitrides, Photocatalyst, Environmental, Treatment, Degradation

Suppressed Dislocation Density in Single-Crystal Pure Ni Fabricated via Laser Powder Bed Fusion with a Flat-Top Laser Profile

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The single-crystal pure Ni with a suppressed dislocation density was fabricated using a laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) process. A flat-top laser profile with a uniform heat intensity distribution along the beam diameter was employed instead of the typical Gaussian profile which has a focused heat intensity in the beam center. The fabrication was performed without any powder stage heating, and a conventional meander scanning with an XY-90° rotation was employed for the scan strategy. Parametric optimizations using the flat-top laser profile resulted in a planar melt pool formation. As a result, a homogeneous near- $\langle 001 \rangle$ single-crystal structure with suppressed high-angle grain boundary (HAGB, misorientation $> 15^\circ$) was obtained at the higher building height of > 20 mm. The single-crystal structure exhibited suppressed strain accumulation and suppressed dislocation density in form of statistically stored dislocation and geometrically necessary dislocation (GND). The GND suppression may have prevented the HAGB formation sourced by continuous dynamic recrystallization. In addition, the shallow melt pool formation caused by the flat-top profile led to lesser thermomechanical cycles during the layer-by-layer building. This may have contributed to the lower strain accumulation and lower dislocation density in the single crystal structure. Furthermore, we observed the proportional relationship between the HAGB density and GND density, suggesting the necessity to control strain accumulation and dislocation density for an LPBF-derived single-crystal structure to be fabricated.

The Stability of Nanobubble Water at Different Temperatures during Long Time Preservation

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Nanobubble water has been applied in many fields due to the unique properties of nanobubble. In this study, three kinds of gas (Air, H₂ and CO₂) nanobubble water were produced. The changes of nanobubble density, size distribution and zeta potential in nanobubble water were investigated under different temperatures (4 °C, 25 °C, and 37 °C) during a two-month storage. The results showed that the temperature has no significant effect on the size distribution of nanobubbles. Nanobubbles are cavities having the diameter of less than 1 micron and filled with gas. They can be suspended in the solutions and are invisible to the naked eye, showing irregular Brownian motion. In particular, little change was noticed on the size of nanobubbles at 4 °C. As for the nanobubble density, a sharp decrease was detected in the air-nanobubble water and H₂-nanobubble water during the first three weeks. After that, the nanobubble density kept relatively stable. Moreover, the reduction rate increased with the increase in storage temperature, about 50% at 4 °C but nearly 80% at 37 °C. The value of zeta potential didn't show remarkable change along with the increase in storage temperature for CO₂-nanobubble water and air-nanobubble water. However, about 25% decrease was detected in the absolute value of zeta potential in H₂-nanobubble water at 25 °C and 37 °C at the end of storage. These findings suggest that nanobubble water is better to be preserved at low temperature for the relatively stable properties of nanobubbles.

Effect of nanobubbles water on microenvironment to improve liver steatosis

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Liver cancer has been concerned in clinical and scientific research, It ranks sixth in cancer incidence and third in mortality worldwide Malignant tumor. Liver steatosis is a largely harmless build-up of fat in the liver cells that may only be diagnosed during tests carried out for another reason. Evidence indicated that the hypoxia in liver microenvironment is one of the most important factors for liver cancer. Nanobubbles water is gas-filled bubbles that spontaneously form at the interface of solid surfaces and aqueous solutions. During the last decade, nanobubbles have already been widely used in the fields of medicine, physiology, and water treatment. In this study, we hypothesize that nanobubbles can change the hypoxia microenvironment in liver microtissue to improve the liver steatosis through inhibition of the secretion of cytokines.

In this study, three kinds of gas (O₂, H₂ and N₂) nanobubble water were produced. The changes of concentration of nanobubbles water(20%,40%,60%,80%,90%). The results showed that the concentration of nanobubbles water has significant effect on the fat accumulation through Nile red staining.

MTT assay was conducted to evaluate the effects of nanobubbles water on the cell viability of human HepG2 cells. The results showed that concentrations of 20%,40%,60%,80%,90% of nanobubbles water did not significantly reduce cell viability throughout 24 h.

Characterization of plasticity initiation phenomena in Zr-based bulk metallic glass via nanoindentation

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Nanoindentation testing (nIIT) can provide precious insights into plastic deformation processes, through the analysis of nIIT loading segment. In bulk metallic glasses (BMG), ‘pop-in’ and serration events are observed and have been linked to plastic deformation processes as shear bands activation. Still, load-displacement ($P-h$) curve fails at displaying these events clearly. The load over displacement vs. displacement curve ($P/h-h$) is a useful tool for an easier visual and quantitative investigation of unstable deformation behavior [1].

The purpose of this study is to investigate plasticity initiation phenomena in a Zr-based bulk metallic glass. Nanoindentation tests are performed in load control mode using a Berkovich indenter (TI 950 Hysitron Triboindenter, Bruker). To ensure statistical significance, 130 tests are performed. Data analysis is performed in the $P/h-h$ curve to detect the point of incipient plasticity, through mathematical and statistical methods [2,3] implemented in a Python code. Three characteristic behaviors are detected on loading curve. One is a deviation from Hertz curve, indicating a local plasticity initiation. Another is a negative slope in a $P/h-h$ curve, suggesting an unstable plastic deformation. The other is a certain displacement of the negative slope in a $P/h-h$ curve, corresponding to a magnitude of the unstable phenomenon. The critical load of the first and second events show a gaussian-like distribution, while the third parameter follows power-law-type probability function.

These results serve as starting point for further discussion on deformation mechanisms involved in incipient plasticity phenomena in BMG.

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Dewatering performance of digested sludge by layered double hydroxides (LDHs) conditioning and its phosphorus recovery potential assessment

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Layered double hydroxides (LDHs), characterized by the brucite-like cationic layers containing anions in the hydrated interlayer, has been demonstrated that it can not only effectively adsorb phosphorus from wastewater as adsorbent material, but also improve sludge dewatering behavior as a chemical conditioner. Additional, its calcined derivatives, known as layered double oxides (LDOs), are composed of mixed metal oxides or spinels, was considered to be higher anion intercalation capacity due to its “memory effect”. In this study, three molar ratio (Mg/Fe=2,3,4) of Mg/Fe-LDHs (M_xF -LDHs) were synthesized at pH=10 using a hydrothermal method to condition digested sludge, Mg/Fe-LDOs were produced under different calcined temperature (250°C, 350°C, 450°C, 550°C, 650°C). The sludge dewatering performance was evaluated by using capillary suction time (CST) and specific resistance to filtration (SRF). The EPS fractions of three layers was extracted and the contents of protein and polysaccharide were also determined. And the structures of layered double hydroxides were characterized by XRD and SEM. The results showed that the sludge was conditioned by M_xF -LDH of Mg/Fe=3 has the best dewatering performances, and the optimal conditions to maximize phosphate adsorption capacity of LDOs were the calcination temperature of 350°C. The M_3F -350 (LDO) exhibited the highest Langmuir maximum adsorption capacity of 99.69 mg-P/g at 25°C. The main mechanisms of phosphate adsorption by LDH are surface complexation, electrostatic interactions, and anion exchange. These results provide a possible way for simultaneous sludge dewatering and phosphorus recovery.

The Physical Features and Stability of Nanobubble Waters in Continuous Observations

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In recent years, nanobubble technology has attracted extensive attention due to its wide application in water treatment, biomedical engineering, nanomaterials, and other scientific and technological fields. Among them, nano-bubble water (NBW) can stay in a relatively stable state for a long period. The average diameter of the nano-bubble is less than or equal to 200 nanometers, with a variety of unique physical properties. The surfaces of NBW are negatively charged (negative zeta potential), and they can remain stable in water for months.

To explore the physical features and the stability state of NBWs, 4 types of NBWs produced from air, hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen gases were used. In this study, Nano-sight has been used to observe the morphology of the nanobubble and calculating the average density and size of these nanobubbles. Zetasizer has been used to measure the zeta potential of the NBWs as a evidence of stability. Also, pH and Dissolved Oxygen (DO), as other paralleled physical feature statistics have been detected. The detection and measurement were conducted 30 minutes after the NBW freshly produced, and start the cycle within 8 times of detections.

The results of this study shows a dynamic stable state of NBWs exists, and being tested for multiple cycles. This will lay the foundation for future research related to the application of NBWs, which is expected to be used in further applications, suggesting more positive potentials.

Fig.1 a The Size of NBWs (nM)

Fig.1 b The Density of NBWs (Particles)

Microstructure Engineering Towards the Development of SmFe₁₂-based Permanent Magnets

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Permanent magnets are materials that can provide magnetic field without need for supply of electric current and are essential components in building energy efficient motors and generators. The Nd₂Fe₁₄B magnets, referred to as Nd-magnets are the most powerful permanent magnets up to now. Fig. 1 compares the ferrite magnets (commonly used on the fridge) and Nd magnets, demonstrating that the Nd-magnets can generate a large magnitude of magnetic field for a small volume of material. However, the price of these magnets is quite high due to the large amount of rare earth (R) Nd (~27 wt.%) used. So, the demand for low-cost permanent magnets has led to a keen interest towards development of R-lean permanent magnets.

A potential permanent magnet candidate must possess the desirable intrinsic hard-magnetic properties such as saturation magnetization, anisotropy field and Curie temperature. Among the several existing potential candidates, the R-lean ThMn₁₂-type compound with the composition Sm(Fe_{0.8}Co_{0.2})₁₁Ti (Sm-based) was found to have a superior combination of intrinsic magnetic properties compared to the Nd₂Fe₁₄B compound [1,2]. Even though the intrinsic magnetic properties are superior, the microstructure of the magnet needs to be tuned for the material to generate magnetic field effectively. In this session, the basics of microstructure engineering and the challenges faced in the development of the Sm-Fe based permanent magnets will be discussed along with some results.

Fig. 1 Comparison of ferrite and Nd-magnets (After Prof. Hono)

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Unraveling how the emission and Raman spectra of $[\text{Au}(\text{SCN})_2]^-$ dimeric and trimeric moieties are affected by aurophillic interaction

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The development of THz sources with intense pulse generation capabilities, and advances in laser optics and narrowband blocking filters allow us to understand the effect of vibrations on molecular properties such as magnetism and luminescence.^[1] Motivated with this idea, we synthesized two set of complexes with dimeric $\{[\text{Au}(\text{SCN})_2]^- \}_2$ and trimeric $\{[\text{Au}(\text{SCN})_2]^- \}_3$ units in the lanthanide matrix with molecular formula $[\text{RE}^{\text{III}}(\text{phen})_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot [\text{Au}^{\text{I}}(\text{SCN})_2]_2 \cdot \text{phen} \cdot 0.5\text{MeCN} \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{RE}^{\text{III}} = \text{Gd}$ (**GdAu2**), Y (**YAu2**)] and $[\text{RE}^{\text{III}}(\text{bpdo})_4] \cdot [\text{Au}^{\text{I}}(\text{SCN})_2]_3 \cdot \text{MeCN}$ [$\text{RE}^{\text{III}} = \text{Gd}$ (**GdAu3**), Y (**YAu3**); phen = 1,10-phenanthroline; bpdo = 2,2'-bipyridyl-*N,N'*-dioxide]. They crystallize into two space groups *P*-1 and *C2/c*, for dimeric and trimeric Au(I) containing cationic units (**Figure 1a, b**).^[2]

Measured temperature-dependent low-frequency Raman spectra reveal several peaks related to the Au...Au stretching modes assigned with the help of quantum chemical calculation. The lowering of temperature reduces the gold-gold bond distance which correlates with a blue shift in the peak position centred around 107 cm^{-1} (**Figure 1c**). Further measured luminescence spectra for different temperatures reveal emission color changing from blue to green via cyan for **GdAu2** and **YAu2** and orangish-white to yellow via several hues of yellow for **GdAu3** and **YAu3**. Emission color changes are ascribable to the appearance of excimer-based triplet emission becoming dominant in the low-temperature region (**Figure 1d**). This also correlates with the cooling of Au...Au vibrational mode at a lower temperature, increasing their quantum yield above 50%. Additionally, by taking the ratio between the high energy peak located at 460 nm and the triplet emission peak centred in the low energy region, we designed high performing ratiometric thermometer in a wide temperature of 10–300 K. The calculated sensitivity was as high as 6.65 and 2.78 % K^{-1} for **GdAu2** and **YAu2**, and 2.45 and 4.49 % K^{-1} for **GdAu3** and **YAu3**. Conclusively, emissive properties of dimeric and trimeric gold(I) centres in two different matrices are sensitive to the association mode in the surrounding through various hydrogen bonds.

Figure 1. The representative crystal structure for **GdAu2** (a) and **GdAu3** (b), temperature-dependent Raman scattering for **GdAu2** (c), and varying emission properties with temperature (d).

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A study of changes in parents' educational psychology caused by changes in educational policies in China and Japan

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At present, China and Japan do not have a clear and unified standard in educational goals, but they are more and more similar in the concept of talent training. For example, "pay attention to the mastery of basic knowledge", "pay attention to the training of ability", "the comprehensive development of knowledge and ability", and "the training of comprehensive talents for the healthy physical and mental development of children". These changes in the concept of talent cultivation, in the final analysis, are caused by the different stages of the "learning ability concept".

A period of "learning ability concept", will affect a period of education reform. Although Japan's "free education" ended, the policy of "free education cancellation," which was reintroduced in 2008, still inherits its core content.

In 2021, China adopted measures to reduce the burden of students' homework and off-campus training courses in compulsory education, or "double reduction". The promulgation of China's "double reduction" policy is also the inheritance and development of the implementation of "burden reduction". The educational policies of the two countries are the product of both the present and the past. At present, China's "double reduction" policy is also the inheritance and development of the previous "burden reduction" policy.

In recent years, while the government's education policy has been revised, "parents' anxiety about education" has been mentioned many times as a hidden indicator to evaluate the level of education. Some studies have shown that "parental anxiety about education" refers to parents' excessive concern about the process and outcome of their children's education in school. This is a general anxiety, common among parents.

Japan has successfully implemented the policy of "free education elimination" for 14 years. At the same time, China, which just implemented the "double reduction" policy, is a good example of how to alleviate parents' anxiety. I think it is very meaningful to find out the reference and contribute to the exchange of education between China and Japan.

Promising Metallo-supramolecular Electrochromic Materials and Devices for Future Smart Window

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With the rapid development of optoelectronic fields, electrochromic (EC) materials and devices have received remarkable attention and have shown attractive potential for use in emerging wearable and portable electronics, electronic papers/billboards, see through displays, other new-generation displays and energy saving smart window due to the advantages of low power consumption, easy viewing, flexibility, stretchability, etc. Intelligent glass facades and smart windows are attracting much interest in contemporary architecture.¹ Electrochromism is a well-known phenomenon capable of providing the required variation in the optical properties, and presently some full-scale electrochromic smart windows are undergoing practical testing in buildings.

Our research background and justification for the development of architectural smart windows². We first note that buildings have windows to allow the occupants visual contact with their surroundings and to provide daylight. From an energy perspective, the window is problematic, though, and it normally either lets in too much energy, so cooling is required to create a good indoor climate, or it lets out too much energy, so heating is needed. In modern commercial buildings, the problem of excessive heating normally dominates, and in the following we only consider cooled buildings. Currently, most EC materials focus on the regulation of visible light. However, nearly 50% of solar energy is located in the near infrared (NIR) region (780–2500 nm) which can pass through glass panels and significantly raise indoor temperatures but has not yet been well controlled in traditional EC devices. These smart windows would contribute to reducing the global energy consumption across building heating and cooling systems by blocking undesired NIR light in summer and intelligently allowing its passage in winter.

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Observation of Isotropic Photonic Double Dirac Cones by High Angle- Resolution Reflection Spectroscopy at the Mid-Infrared Frequencies

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Dirac cones at the center of reciprocal space (the Γ point) are a special feature of periodic structures¹. They are a pair of linear dispersions crossing at a point called the Dirac point, in an otherwise symmetrical parabolic dispersion relation. The effective refractive index vanishes at the Dirac point leading to peculiar phenomena in photonics, such as optical cloaking, scatter-free waveguides, and beam shaping^{2,3}.

Double Dirac cones can be materialized on the Γ point of C_{6v} -symmetric periodic structures, by the accidental degeneracy of E_1 & E_2 modes upon altering the structural parameters¹, necessitating challenging high precision nanofabrication. Their clear experimental observation is difficult due to the proximity with neighboring modes. We present the first measurement of a photonic double Dirac cone on the Γ point of C_{6v} -symmetric photonic crystals by high angle resolution reflection spectroscopy at infrared frequencies. In this work, we realized double Dirac cones in 2-dimensional photonic crystal slabs, isolated by the unique design², with specimen fabricated in silicon (Fig. 1(a, b)). We experimentally obtained an isotropic dispersion relation of the double Dirac cones by mapping the measured reflection spectra (shown in Fig.1 (c) using high angle-resolution (0.3°) set-up⁴. This work achieves photonic Dirac cones by integrating cutting-edge nanofabrication and high-precision measurements.

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Figure 1. (a) SEM of top-view of a unit cell, and (b) the cross-sectional SEM of the photonic crystal slabs fabricated in the top silicon layer of an SOI wafer. (c) The reflection spectra of the sample in IR frequency, measured at a high-angle resolution of 0.3° , measured from incident angles($=\theta$) -3.5° to 3.5° .

Construction of *in vivo* system for predicting human CYP24A1-dependent metabolism

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Vitamin D3 is metabolized to 25-hydroxyvitamin D3 (25D3) in the liver, and further metabolized in the kidney to 1 α ,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 (1,25D3), which exerts various physiological effects such as bone formation, calcium homeostasis, cell proliferation and differentiation, and so on, by binding vitamin D receptor (VDR). Thus, 1,25D3 and its analogs have been clinically used as therapeutic agents against rickets, psoriasis, and secondary hyperparathyroidism, and they have been also expected as cancer treatments. When 1,25D3 and its analogs bind to VDR, CYP24A1 is also transcriptional activated and the overexpressed CYP24A1 enzyme inactivate them. Thus, resistance to CYP24A1-dependent metabolism could be a key property in prolonging their biological effects.

We have established the *in vitro* and *in vivo* system to evaluate CYP24A1 metabolism of each vitamin D analogs, including recombinant CYP24A1 expression system and CYP24A1-knockout (KO) rats¹. CYP24A1 shows the species-based differences between rats and humans; human CYP24A1 catalyzes both C-23 and C-24 oxidation pathways, whereas rat CYP24A1 shows almost no C-23 oxidation pathway.

The final goal of this study is to generate humanized CYP24A1 rats by introducing recombinant adeno-viral vector harboring human CYP24A1 cDNA to CYP24A1 KO rats, for predicting vitamin D analogs in humans. In this presentation, I will talk about the basic results for above study such as metabolic study of keratinocytes prepared from wild-type and CYP24A1 KO rats.

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Figure 1. Metabolic pathway of 1,25D3 by CYP24A1

Analog/RF Performance Analysis of GaSb-InP Vertical Tunnel Field Effect Transistors

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This article investigates the performance of a vertically grown GaSb/InP tunnel field effect transistor (VTFET) with a source pocket to enhance the performance of the device. However, band-to-band tunneling (BTBT), the physical principle responsible for the current transport in a conventional TFET, inherently supports a low ON-current (I_{ON}). A low bandgap material, GaSb, is used in the source region to enhance the carrier tunneling through the source (GaSb)-channel (InP) heterojunction. The proposed VTFET with a pocket presents the improved parameters comparison as given in Table I. From the fabrication point of view, the VTFET is easier to fabricate than the conventional TFETs, the result also shows that the proposed device outperforms and it can be a better alternative for future low power applications.

Parameters	I_{ON} (A/ μ m)	I_{OFF} (A/ μ m)	g_m (μ S/ μ m)	Avg. SS(mV/dec)	f_T (GHz)
Ref [1]	1.9×10^{-6}	2.0×10^{-17}	7	79.8	0.7
Ref [2]	1.8×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-16}	74	40.44	0.17
This work	4.62×10^{-5}	2.12×10^{-17}	125	27	57

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Phosphorus-decorated Mo-MXene/CQD hybrid: a 2D/0D architecture for bifunctional electrochemical water splitting

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The exploration of nonprecious metal-based 2D bifunctional electrocatalysts is of great significance for transforming to sustainable energies in terms of hydrogen. However, to achieve commendable electrocatalytic performance via rational design of surface-interface-engineered Mo-MXene hybrids remain challenging and highly demanding. Herein, we report large size exfoliated Mo-MXene sheets, which provide a flat flexible interface for decoration with carbon quantum dots (CQDs) and controlled surface phosphorization (denoted as Mo-MX/C/P hybrid). The resulting Mo-MX/C/P hybrid exhibited the lowest onset potentials of 14 and 58 mV at an applied current of 0.2 mA cm^{-2} for the HER and OER, respectively. Strikingly, the electronegative nature of phosphorous (P) and quick charge transfer between the CQDs and Mo₂CT_x matrix were responsible for its superior catalytic activities. Despite the superior performance, the Mo-MX/C/P hybrid can also be used for full-cell division of water with a cell voltage of 1.34 volts at 10 mA cm^{-2} and was found to be durable up to 12. This work provides a novel insight into the further development of surface-interface-engineered Mo-MXene hybrids for sustainable energy.

Chromaticity Tunable White-Light-Emitting Carbon Dots via N-Dopant Site Formulation

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Doped carbon dot (CD) is a revolutionary materials for the rare-earth and toxic metal-free lighting material which are composed mainly of C, O, H, and N. The emission property is tuned by the doping centre and surface functional groups leading to multi-coloured emission. The N-doping centre has provided a vital role of the emission property.^[1-2] The optimized synthetic strategy enabled us to tune the N doping sites and lead to the broadband emission as a result direct WLE (400 to 750 nm). The controlling the N doped sites into the CDs led to the green to red emission. Here, we combined the ¹⁵N SS-NMR with XPS spectra to evaluate the local N doping environment to understand the emission property of rationally designed NCDs to produces the direct WLE. As synthesized CDs show direct and ideal WLE both in solution and in solid forms with CIE coordinates value of (0.34, 0.36) and high colour rendering index (CRI 92) via controlling the doing sites (Fig. 1 a-b). The local N doping sites of CDs are identified by combining both XPS and SS-NMR spectroscopy. This study delivers vital guiding principles for synthesis of multicolor to WLE CDs by realizing the N doping sites (Fig. 1 c).

Fig.1: (a-b) Emission spectra of different types of CDs and their corresponding CIE diagram. (c) Identification of N doping sites of different types of CDs.

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Giant Spin Pumping at Ferromagnet (Permalloy) - Organic Semiconductor (Perylene diimide) Interface

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Understanding the spin current transport in non-magnetic materials is essential for the design and development of spintronic devices. So far heavy metals (HM) are used in most of the spintronic devices as non-magnetic layers because of the high spin-orbit coupling (SOC). However, for the very same reason, HM does not possess good spin diffusion length and long spin-relaxation time. On the other hand, organic semiconductors (OSC) can host spin current with a large spin diffusion length and long spin-relaxation time due to relatively low SOC. In addition to that, tunability of SOC in OSCs make them a potential contender for HM. In this work, we have employed a robust perylene diimide (PDI) shown in Fig.1(a) which is an n-type organic semiconductor as a non-magnetic material to host spin current. We have deposited various thickness of permalloy (Py or Ni₈₀Fe₂₀) on spin coated PDI (Si/PDI) using magnetron sputtering. Through spin-pumping technique using ferromagnetic resonance (FMR), we have successfully injected spin currents from permalloy (FM) into adjacent PDI(OSC) layer as shown in Fig.1(a). We have confirmed the spin injection through linewidth broadening associated with FMR, which is widely accepted as a direct method to validate spin injection.[1] The linewidth broadening is consistently observed in all the samples of PDI/Py(t) where the thickness of Py is 4, 8, 12 and 16 nm. The observed FMR associated linewidth broadening is found to be one order higher (0.53-2.18 mT) than what is reported (0.05 mT) earlier in FM/OSC bilayers [2]. We have quantified the amount of the spin current injected via spin mixing conductance ($g_{\uparrow\downarrow}$) by fitting α_{eff} vs $1/t_{\text{FM}}$ to equation (1) and it is found to be $1.54 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ which is in the similar order of FM/Heavy metal bilayer structures.

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} = \alpha_0 + \frac{\gamma \hbar g_{\uparrow\downarrow}}{4\pi M_s t_{\text{FM}}} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. (a) Molecular structure and schematic representation of PDI, (b) Schematic illustration of device architecture used for spin pumping experiments under FMR conditions. (c) FMR spectra showing change in linewidth.

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Effect of Pore Size Distribution on Carbon Dioxide Adsorption in Activated Carbon: A Grand Canonical Monte Carlo Simulation Study

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Adsorption based carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology is becoming a promising alternative to solvent absorption techniques due to its low energy consumption for material regeneration. Activated carbons as adsorbent material are gaining increasing attention for their relatively lower production cost and ease of cyclic regeneration. Experimental characterization of the adsorption process fails to segregate the influence of the pore size distribution and chemical nature of the adsorbent surface on the adsorption performance. A molecular level investigation of the adsorption process can elucidate the contribution of these adsorbent properties. Studies on the molecular simulation of adsorption process involving zeolite and metal organic framework are ubiquitous. Conversely, the effect of the pore size distribution of activated carbon on the CO₂ adsorption process has rarely been analyzed. Therefore, in this study, a molecular simulation-based adsorption characterization with different pore sizes has been performed. A reduced pore size favors the adsorption process via an increased isosteric heat of adsorption. Thus, the adsorption uptake rapidly elevates at a lower pressure for lower pore sizes. However, a lower pore size significantly affects the maximum adsorption capacity of the adsorbent. The effect of functional groups on the CO₂ adsorption performance can be further investigated, which can act as a benchmark for advanced adsorbent development.

The possibility of the gene therapy for rickets type II alopecia using adenovirus vector

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Type II rickets is a hereditary disease caused by a mutation in the vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene. The main symptoms are bone dysplasia and alopecia. While there is symptomatic treatment by high calcium intake for the former, there is currently no cure for the latter. Therefore, in this study, we verified whether gene therapy using adenovirus vector [1] on type II rickets model rat (VDR-KO rat) [2] could provide a therapeutic effect on alopecia.

The 7-weeks-old female VDR-KO rats were divided to 2 groups, one is a VDR-expressing adenovirus vector (VDR-adenovirus)—administered (n=2), the other is non-administered (n=1). First, the hair on the backs of 4 rats including wild-type rat (n=1) were shaved to the same extent with hair clippers, and then about 1.0×10^{10} pfu of VDR-adenovirus was intradermally administered to 2 rats. Skin was collected from each rat at 2 days and 10 days after adeno-administration, and the state of hair growth and hair loss was observed. As a result, in the adeno-administered group showed hair growth promotion, hair loss suppression, and cyst formation suppression around the administration sites. However, no such phenomena were observed in VKO-control rat. These results suggest the possibility of gene therapy using VDR-expressing adenovirus vector for type II rickets model rats.

Our final goal is to realize genome-editing therapy for rickets type II alopecia, using adenovirus vector with CRISPR-Cas9 system.

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Drought Impact Assessment Using Multivariate Drought Index and Relation with Socioeconomic Security of Farmers

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Droughts are complex, multidimensional and spatially extensive water extreme events. Among all the natural disasters, droughts are responsible for majority of the damage worldwide, where its frequency and severity is expected to increase in the future pertaining to the warming climate. In India, more than 80% of the population lives in districts vulnerable to droughts where agriculture sector and consequently farmers often face the dire consequences of droughts such as agriculture failures, water scarcity and economic losses threatening the socioeconomic security of farmers. Maharashtra state in particular is highly infamous for deteriorating farmers' status, visible in the form of farmer suicides. India being an agrarian country, drought assessment thus holds a paramount importance. The drought mitigation in India is based on the manual of drought management where the declaration of drought is a crucial step in initiating the state relief measures. Multiple climatic and hydrologic factors are responsible for droughts and vegetation conditions, where identification of the primary drought drivers and understanding of their integrated effect is very important for holistic drought quantification. Despite the process of drought management by the manual being comprehensive, pertaining to the univariate system of drought analysis, the process has its own limitations where, this integrated effect is often neglected, frequently leading to ambiguous drought categorization.

In the present study, dynamics and variability in vegetation were analyzed in the form of greening and browning trends along with discerning the governing factors and their possible implications on the farmers in the Maharashtra state of India. Furthermore, using the confounding primary drought drivers, a novel multivariate Joint Drought Index (JDI) was proposed for seasonal agriculture drought classification which shall provide a unique perspective for drought monitoring and mitigation by increasing the accuracy of drought severity analysis in India and beyond. Moreover, taking farmers suicide as an index showing the socioeconomic status of farmers, the possible relation between vegetation trend and dynamics and role of JDI in the farmer's socioeconomic status is also discussed.

Low concentrated ions detection in complex medium with high ionic strength: example of cesium detection in seawater

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Lot of progress have been achieved in biosensors in the last years: they have higher sensitivity, better limit of detection, larger panel of target analyte, reduced cost, etc. Among these features, the detection in complex medium is often poorly studied. Herein we demonstrate the efficient fabrication of a novel electrolyte-gated organic field-effect transistor sensor for the Cs⁺ detection in seawater based on the combination of two ultra-thin layers namely poly(3-hexylthiophene) as semiconductor and a single lipids monolayer as dielectric. The latter is end-capped with a specific Cs⁺ probe based on a calix[4] arene benzo crown ether to ensure the selectivity. Cs⁺ sensing experiments were performed in various conditions, including the presence of competitive ions and/or solutions with very high ionic strength. Interestingly, we clearly evidence that by controlling affinity driven guest/host ion exchange, one can lift the general problem of selectivity encountered in all FET-based ion sensors, reaching selectivity even in highly complex analytes, such as phosphate buffered saline solution or seawater. Also, our ultra-thin transistor structure exhibits, a limit of detection at the attomolar level which corresponds to a 5 folds' magnitude lower than Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy, the most commonly used technic today. Such low limit of detection cannot be explained solely by the change in surface potential induced by the capture of ions by the probe; instead, we suggest a reorientation of the dipoles moments at the probe level that may propagate on a large distance leading to an enhancement of the surface potential change induced by an initial ion/probe complexation event. These results are showing a solution for the detection and quantification of Cs⁺ in aquatic media, tackling an environmental safety and public health matter, and paving the way to a generalized monitoring of ions in complexed analytes.

Figure 1 : A) EG-OFET sensor design based on ultra-thin layers of P3HT and engineered lipid monolayer as semiconducting and dielectric materials respectively. The Cesium probe is a calix[4]arene benzocrown ether grafted to the lipid monolayer through a triethoxysilane groups. B) Picture of a chip containing 8 transistors mounted in parallel. C) Picture of the set-up for electrical measurements. E) Comparison of the performances of EG-OFET sensor (in blue) with ICP-MS based detection (red).

Unveiling charge carrier distribution in Al doped SrTiO₃ photocatalyst with quantum efficiency of unity

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Photocatalytic water splitting is a promising candidate to produce hydrogen fuel from sunlight and water at a large scale.¹ The development of this green technology is imperative to meet growing energy demands and reduce greenhouse gas emissions globally. For cost-effective hydrogen generation, the demonstration of high quantum efficiency is essential and remains challenging for the research community. Recently, our group realized Al-doped SrTiO₃ (Al:STO) material for solar water splitting with external quantum efficiency (EQE) of 96 % at wavelength between 350 nm to 360 nm.² High EQE was achieved by selective deposition of Rh/CoO_x and CoOOH co-catalysts on different facets of crystalline Al:STO particles.

In this work, we developed a semiconductor device model to unravel the governing energetic and charge carrier distribution behind the high quantum efficiency of Al:STO photocatalysts.² Our results (in Fig. 1) revealed that the work function difference (by facet engineering) induced an asymmetric upward and downward band bending at respective {110} and {100} facets.² The asymmetric band bending induced the selective transport of electrons and holes for hydrogen and oxygen evolution reaction at {100} and {110} facets, respectively. Such anisotropic charge transport increases with the increase of work function difference between facets.

Fig. 1. Mapping of **a**, conduction energy band E_c , **b**, electron density n , and **c**, hole density p . **d**, Energy band diagram. **e**, n and p distribution. **f**, Work function difference DW_{el} versus n/p or p/n at {100} and {110} facets.

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Nanocrystalline Soft Magnetic Material for Automotive Applications

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High-performance soft magnetic materials play a significant role in improving the energy efficiency, performance, and miniaturization of electromechanical and power electronics devices. By the enormous energy consumption due to the modern lifestyle, even a small improvement in material performance can have a huge impact on savings and the overall economy. Non-oriented Si-steel, known as “electrical steels,” having 3 – 3.5 wt.% Si with magnetic induction in the range of 1.8 – 2.0 T is widely used on account of its acceptable electrical and magnetic properties. The Si content beyond 3.5 % in Fe is advantageous to obtain low core loss; however, processing such high Si content alloys by wrought product route has been unsuccessful due to the inadequate ductility and limited formability of these alloys ^[1]. With the advent of electric and hybrid electric vehicles (EV/HEV) in the automotive industry, rising demand for high-performance soft magnetic materials as an alternative to Si steel leads to an upsurge in research activities.

A wide range of soft magnetic materials was extensively investigated but restricted to limited applications ^[1]. Similar to Si-steels, Fe-P-based alloys have promising characteristics; the addition of a small percentage of P to Fe enhances the electrical resistivity and reduces the core loss without significant reduction in the saturation magnetization. This can be attributed to the presence of Fe₃P nanoprecipitates in the α -Fe matrix ^[2]. The processing of Fe-P alloy using the wrought metallurgy route (melting, forging, and rolling) is difficult due to the P segregation at grain boundaries. However, a controlled process flow chart can produce Fe-P-based nanocrystalline alloy using a wrought alloy process. In the presentation, I will discuss the details of composition-process-microstructure-property correlation to obtain the optimum soft magnetic properties and its scientific & technological importance for automotive applications.

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Rational design of two-dimensional multi-metallic based nanostructures for efficient water oxidation

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Hydrogen is a green alternative to depleting fossil fuel-based energy resources. Hydrogen can be produced either by steam reforming or water splitting. The former diminishes the environmental merits of hydrogen energy by releasing carbon monoxide or carbon dioxide as byproducts. However, water splitting is a clean technology consisting of hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER). OER is a much complex kinetics involving multiple electron transfer process and hence designing an efficient catalyst for OER is the bottleneck. Ru and Ir based oxides have been considered as potential electrocatalysts to drive OER. A cost effective alternative include first row transition metal based oxides/hydroxides. Herein, we have synthesized 2-dimensional (2D) trimetallic Co, Ni and Mn oxide-hydroxide using simple one pot solution technique which show enhanced current density, low onset and overpotential, excellent operational stability and durability. Detailed investigations (X-Ray absorption spectroscopy, X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy, Mott-Schottky analysis, electrochemical surface area analysis, etc) revealed the enhanced OER performance is due to the improved intrinsic and extrinsic activity of the trimetallic system over the bimetallic counterparts. Improved conductivity and low activation energy of the trimetallic was responsible for the favourable reaction kinetics. Hence, designing multielement transition metal-based catalysts, with careful elemental choice can yield a potential candidate for water oxidation.

How Emotions Improve Music Generation

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Music is language agnostic. Despite language barriers, we share the universal experience of music. With a rich history of its own, the music production industry is now shifting trends with the wave of digitisation.

One of the more popular goals for the future of music is **automated music generation**. Many research studies have employed machine learning models to artificially generate music. However, the generated music still lacks the quality we find in human-composed music. Some of the concerns include global coherence (musicality) and emotional impact [1].

We plan to address this research gap by conditioning music generation with emotions. Sentiment is an overlooked aspect to the quality of music. We hypothesized that conditioning on emotions should improve the musicality of the AI generated music. Hence, **we propose a conditioned Transformer - Generative Adversarial Network (Trans-GAN) model that generates music conditioned on the input emotion**. Due to resource constraints, our model has roughly 10 times less trainable parameters compared to the baseline [1]. This gives us an opportunity to explore the quality of generated music within the resource limit.

We investigated the effects of different music representation, architecture, datasets, hyperparameters and loss functions on the performance of the model. The performance was evaluated using musical metrics, Negative Log Likelihood (NLL) loss and a subjective test. We compared our results with existing unconditioned and conditioned models. We found that our model achieved an **NLL of 1.2, lower than the unconditioned Trans-GAN**. Moreover, the generated music also attained the **highest emotion classification accuracy**. Subjective tests indicate that the model has potential to generate human-like music, with particular success in valence-rich (positive) music, however needs longer training sequences for effective musicality.

We hope to inspire people to pursue research despite resource constraints. We aim that in our pursuit, we can build a new wave of creativity with machines-humans collaboration.

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Characterization Of the Sulfide-Responsive Transcriptional Factor YgaV In *Escherichia coli*.

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Oxygen is one of the most important parameters for all living things and microbes, and it regulates bacterial metabolism. *Escherichia coli*, an enteric bacterium, thrives in the gastrointestinal tracts of humans and other warm-blooded animals, alongside pathogenic and commensal bacteria. In such a gastrointestinal environment, oxygen is always a limiting factor for generating energy through respiration. As a result, when oxygen levels are low, the intestinal bacterium *E. coli* switches from aerobic to anaerobic respiration. Recent research indicates that hydrogen sulfide and reactive sulfur species are involved in this switching, but the exact mechanism is still unclear. We recently discovered the hydrogen sulfide responsive transcription factor SqrR from the purple photosynthetic bacterium *Rhodospirillum rubrum* that uses H₂S as an electron donor. Interestingly, the SqrR homologs were also found in gut microbiota, including *E. coli*. Therefore, we proceed with the functional analysis of SqrR homolog, YgaV, in *E. coli*. We have discovered that YgaV controls the expression of genes involved in anaerobic respiration. Furthermore, when growing in the H₂S atmosphere, wildtype *E. coli* has increased antibiotic resistance compared to the *ygaV* mutant. According to the above results, YgaV-dependent transcriptional regulation increases antibiotic resistance by controlling the switch between aerobic and anaerobic respiration, maintaining redox homeostasis, and reducing the production of reactive sulfur species.

Sea level variability along the western coast of India simulated in a high-resolution ocean general circulation model

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Future sea level change projections using climate models have progressed over the years (e.g., IPCC Sixth Assessment Report). However, the resolution is insufficient to adequately represent coastal phenomena. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct downscaling using high-resolution ocean general circulation models (OGCM) to create a dataset that can assess the risk of sea level rise in coastal areas under global warming. In this study, we conduct simulations to reproduce past sea level variations along the western coast of India using an eddy-resolving OGCM.

First, we examined the differences in resolution and found that the high-resolution OGCM reduces biases of sea surface temperature and sea surface height (SSH) over the global ocean. Next, the reproducibility of sea level variations along the western coast of India was examined. It is found that the phase and amplitude of the seasonal variations as well as the probability distribution of the intra-seasonal variations are significantly improved in the high-resolution OGCM. Previous studies reported that coastal Kelvin waves originating from the tropical Indian Ocean are thought to explain about 50~70% of the intra-seasonal variability of SSH variations along the western coast of India (e.g., Suresh et al. 2013; 2016; 2018). Therefore, we investigated the sources of the SSH variation at 15°N in models and found significant propagations of coastal Kelvin waves in the equatorial Indian Ocean and the Bay of Bengal only in the high-resolution OGCM. On the other hand, low-resolution OGCM did not reproduce the propagation of SSH variation from the equatorial Indian Ocean to the western coast of India due to the lack of horizontal resolution.

The effect of β/α strength ratio and volume fraction of β for fatigue properties of Ti-alloys

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Near α -Ti alloys are widely used in high temperature components such as compressors of aircraft engines. Fatigue fracture is the most serious problem in near α -Ti alloys. It is well known that the lifetime of dwell fatigue, holding at maximum stress during each loading cycle, is drastically reduced compared with that of normal fatigue, simple cyclic loading [1]. Near α -Ti alloys are composed of equiaxed hcp- α phase and α /bcc- β lamellar structure in order to balance creep and fatigue properties. Dwell fatigue has been discussed in terms of the crystal orientation of α grains against a loading axis [2]. It is also suggested that a microcrack initiates in a thin β grain and propagates along the basal planes in neighboring α grains during fatigue [3]. Even though β phase effects on fatigue properties were reported, the study of β phase effect on dwell fatigue is not sufficient. Therefore, clarifying the effect of β phase on fatigue properties is necessary.

In this study, we aim to investigate the effect of strength ratio (= β phase strength per α phase strength) and volume fraction of β phase on fatigue crack initiation and propagation by utilizing the fatigue test using three different alloys, (1) Ti-Fe (β phase is much stronger than α phase), (2) Ti-Al-Fe (β phase is stronger than α phase), and (3) Ti-Al-V (α phase is stronger than β phase). About Ti-Al-Fe and Ti-Al-V, three types of composition on tie-lines were made to change volume fraction. By comparing the results of each alloy, we analyzed the effect of the strength ratio and volume fraction of β phase.

All samples were prepared by cold crucible levitation melting and were heat-treated in the $\alpha+\beta$ phase region. The normal and dwell fatigue tests were performed using the load controlling mode for the prepared alloy. The maximum stress of $\sigma_{0.98}$ for the 0.2 % flow stress was applied at room temperature. The stress ratio between the maximum and minimum stresses was $R=0.1$. The sign curve with 5 Hz was used for the normal fatigue test and the trapezoidal wave with a holding time of 120 s was used for the dwell fatigue test. Microstructure, crystal orientation, and strain distribution of fractured samples were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) equipped with electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD).

Heat-treated microstructure is shown in Fig.1. All alloys are composed of equiaxed α and β phases with grain size between a few μm to 10 μm . The volume fraction of β phase increased with the increase of the amount of Fe and V. Longer dwell fatigue life was observed in alloys with the increase of the volume fraction of the weak phase. Strain distribution after failure was investigated mainly for dwell fatigue. It indicated that high strength ratio caused inhomogeneous deformation in α and β phases and this makes crack initiation easier at the interface between α and β phase.

Fig.1. Microstructure of the tested samples.

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Functional Analysis of Chloride Ion Channel *Clic1* in Cancer Invasion

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As of 2020, there were 2.3 million new cases of breast cancer globally and over 280,000 diagnosed in 2022 within the US itself. Fortunately, this is manageable if it is detected in the localized stages before metastasis occurs. This metastasis begins with cancer cell invasion through the narrow spaces between cells. *Clic1*, a type of chloride (Cl^-) ion channel, is overexpressed in the tumor cells and involved in the invasion process. Additionally, *Clic1* also plays an important role in regulatory volume decrease (RVD), in which the efflux of Cl^- and K^+ ions promote the efflux of water molecules and reduces the cell volume. Based on these reports, we hypothesize that *Clic1* exports Cl^- ions through stretch of the cell membrane during the invasion process, thereby decreasing the volume of cancer cells by RVD and promoting invasion. Furthermore, we considered that Cl^- ion efflux in cancer cells could be induced even by simple mechanical stress.

In this study, we simulated this environment using atomic force microscopy to apply mechanical force to human breast cancer cell lines of different invasiveness. N-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-6-methoxyquinolinium bromide (MQAE), a membrane-permeable fluorescent indicator that quenches by interaction with Cl^- ions, was added to the culture medium and incubated for 1 h to introduce MQAE into the cells. We observed that fluorescence intensity of intracellular MQAE increased on application of mechanical force. This result indicates that the efflux of Cl^- ion can be induced by applying external mechanical force to cancer cell. This Cl^- ion efflux ability showed a positive correlation with the invasion ability of the cancer cells, suggesting that the invasiveness of cancer cells could be evaluated by Cl^- efflux ability.

Potassium-based Dual Carbon Battery using Pure Ionic Liquid Electrolyte

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Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) available today have two major issues: first, the depleting and localized lithium and cobalt resources resulting in increased prices; and second, the risk of fire hazard due to the utilization of organic solvent electrolytes. Dual-carbon batteries (DCBs) have been garnering considerable attention due to their advantages of being environmentally friendly, economical, and providing a high cost-to-performance ratio. Moreover, the abundant potassium resources and the safety of ionic liquid (IL) electrolytes make them potential candidates for next-generation batteries [1]. Therefore, we have focused on the development of potassium-based DCB in coin cell configuration which delivers enhanced capacity and promising cycling performance, using K[FTA]–[C₄C₁pyrr][FTA] (FTA = (fluorosulfonyl)(trifluorosulfonyl)amide; C₄C₁pyrr = *N*-butyl-*N*-methylpyrrolidinium) IL electrolyte and natural graphite as both positive and negative electrode material. In this study, dual carbon cells exhibited an initial high discharge capacity of 81 mAh g⁻¹ at a current rate of 1C (1C = 100 mA g⁻¹) in a voltage range of 3.0–5.35 V and 298 K temperature. *Ex-situ* X-ray diffraction measurements were conducted for K/graphite (positive and negative electrode) half cells to investigate the intercalation of FTA⁻ anions and K⁺ cations into graphite electrodes respectively.

Fig. 1 (a) Initial charge–discharge curves of graphite (positive)/graphite (negative) dual carbon cell using K[FTA]–[C₄C₁pyrr][FTA] ($x(\text{K}[\text{FTA}]) = 0.20$) IL electrolyte at a current rate of 1C at 298 K. (b) Long-term cycling properties of dual carbon cells at a current rate of 1C and 298 K.

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Stiffness Analysis via Atomic Force Microscopy for Microneedle Arrays-Assisted Direct Delivery of Genome Editing Machinery in Rice

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CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing has been widely used in agriculture to develop gene-edited plants that confer the trait of interest. In Japan, genome-edited plants with deletions of one to several dozen bases in the genomic DNA sequence are not considered genetically modified organisms because they are indistinguishable from plants with mutations that exist in nature. Plant transformation methods via *Agrobacterium*-mediated and biolistics are commonly applied to introduce DNA constructs expressing CRISPR machinery into the host genome. Therefore, it is necessary to remove the vector-derived DNA from genome DNA by backcrossing. In contrast, direct delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complexes to plant cells for targeted mutation, or DNA-free approach, does not have this problem. To transport RNP while overcoming the plant cell wall barrier, microneedles array (MNA)-assisted direct delivery has been demonstrated in dicot, *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf and shoot apical meristem (SAM) of soybean, in our previous study. Here, we evaluated the potential application of MNA in the model plant for monocot, *Oryza sativa* L. cv. Nipponbare, based on the stiffness analysis of the rice tissues. Two types of rice tissues, embryogenic callus and coleoptile, were evaluated via atomic force microscopy at a setpoint of 20 nN and an approach speed of 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ using the cantilever with a triangular pyramidal shape tip. As a result, Young's modulus of coleoptile tissue was similar to that of *A. thaliana* leaf and soybean SAM. In contrast, rice callus has a ten times higher stiffness than coleoptile tissue. This result suggests that rice callus may have higher resistance for MNA insertion than coleoptile tissue. Thus, MNA-assisted RNP delivery in dicot can be applied for coleoptile tissues whereas optimization is needed for rice callus.

Keywords: CRISPR/Cas9, Plant transformation, DNA-free, Microneedles array, Atomic force microscopy

Physics from Belle II experiment, status and prospects

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The Belle II experiment at the SuperKEKB energy-asymmetric e^+e^- collider is a substantial upgrade of the B factory facility at the Japanese High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK) laboratory. The design luminosity of the machine is $6 \times 10^{35} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and the Belle II experiment aims to ultimately record 50 ab^{-1} of data, a factor of 50 more than its predecessor. After a substantial upgrade of the detector and the accelerator, the machine commissioning has been completed in 2018 and the data taking has begun since then. The Belle II has accumulated more than $\sim 424 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ of data so far.

The rate of semileptonic and electroweak penguin decays in the B sector show hints of lepton-flavor-universality violation. Belle and Belle II data is well suited to probe such anomalies. These B decays attract significant attention due to several observed discrepancies between the standard-model predictions and the results. The low-background collision environment along with the possibility of partially or fully reconstructing one of the two B mesons in the event offer high precision measurements of semileptonic and electroweak B decays. This talk presents recent Belle and Belle II results lepton flavor universality tests and prospects.

Hydrogen peroxide evolution via Electrocatalytic Two-electron Water Oxidation by Zinc Porphyrin

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Abstract

Artificial Photosynthesis is an effective way to harness solar energy and solve energy crisis problem. Metalloporphyrins are a well-known candidate for alternative artificial photosynthetic strategy for H₂O₂ production. Visible light-induced oxygen evolution from water via four-electron process, suffers bottle-neck in the field of artificial photosynthesis, termed as Photon-flux density problem. One-photon initiated two-electron water oxidation despite of its less attention, are ideal to solve this bottleneck, yielding energetically superior products than four-electron process.¹ To date, various earth-abundant metalloporphyrins have been studied on two-electron water oxidation in our group. However, the renewable energy factor plays an important role when it comes to the realization of this system.²

This study reveals the facile, environmentally benign and cost-effective synthesis of zinc-based metalloporphyrin, ZnTMPyP in water at ambient temperature. Through various spectroscopic analytical techniques and fluorescence life time analysis axial ligand characteristics and protolytic species of ZnTMPyP were analyzed. One-electron initiated electrochemical water oxidation were examined using electrochemical analysis. The source of oxygen in two-electron water oxidation products were confirmed by isotope labelled experiments using O-18 labeled water. Electron spin population in intermediate species through DFT calculation as well as proposed mechanism for the electrochemical water oxidation are also discussed.³

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